

PROGRAMA CIENTÍFICO SCIENTIFIC PROGRAMME

18.^a EDIÇÃO

ENCONTRO
INVESTIGAÇÃO
JOVEM

7, 8 e 9 MAIO 2025

ICBAS | UNIVERSIDADE
FFUP | DO PORTO

Organização

Apoio

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BOAS-VINDAS | WELCOME

Temos assistido nos últimos tempos a um conjunto de desenvolvimentos inesperados que de alguma forma questionam a liberdade académica, a procura de conhecimento e os indubitáveis avanços científicos. É por isso uma enorme satisfação constatar o interesse dos jovens da nossa universidade pela atividade científica, que nesta 18ª edição do IJUP – Encontro de Investigação Jovem da Universidade do Porto se mobilizaram apresentando mais de seiscentos e cinquenta projetos de investigação.

A Universidade do Porto tem entre os seus objetivos providenciar uma formação científica, técnica e ética de excelência, e capaz de, com o enquadramento e a orientação dos nossos docentes e investigadores, potenciar a natural ousadia e a criatividade dos jovens estudantes da melhor universidade portuguesa. Os trabalhos de investigação que aqui se dão a conhecer constituem, por isso, uma muito significativa mostra da estreita ligação que procuramos estabelecer (e estimular) entre a formação académica e a investigação científica.

Não me esqueço de que estes resultados, bem como os seus futuros desenvolvimentos, apenas são possíveis graças à dedicação e ao apoio de uma vasta equipa, cujo trabalho quero naturalmente agradecer e sublinhar. O mérito maior pertence, todavia, a todos aqueles cujos trabalhos foram selecionados para esta edição do IJUP, aos quais felicito pela qualidade da investigação produzida nas mais diversas áreas do conhecimento. O potencial científico e criativo demonstrado pelos estudantes da U.Porto permite-nos ter a certeza não só de que a ciência não tem idade, mas também de que as próximas gerações de investigadores estão plenamente capacitadas para impulsionar o avanço do conhecimento e o progresso da comunidade que temos o dever de servir.

Pedro Rodrigues

Vice-Reitor para a Investigação e Inovação

Universidade do Porto

Quarta-feira, 7 de maio | Wednesday, May 7th

08:00 - 18:00 Secretariado a todos os participantes/ *Secretariat for all participants*

09:00 - 10:30 PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS I

Room A1 – Health Sciences I

22804 | The Invisibility of VBNC Pathogens in Standard Food Safety Protocols

Ferreira, Beatriz; Barata, Rita; Oliveira, M. Beatriz P. P.; Almeida, Gonçalo

22957 | Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) for *Enterobacter cloacae* complex species differentiation: a promising tool for rapid identification

Martins, Rita; Goncalves, Ana B.; Hernandez-García, Marta; Silva, Luís M.; Castro, Ana P.; Read, Maria A.; Alves, Valquíria; Cantón, Rafael; Peixe, Luísa; Novais, Ângela

23074 | Going down the rabbit hole – Screening of coronaviruses in European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus algirus*) populations from Portugal

Lapa, Inês; Almeida, Tereza; Lopes, Ana M.; Abrantes, Joana

23105 | Shedding Light on Bacterial Resistance: Evaluating the Sublethal Effects of Light-Activated Graphene

Lázaro, Beatriz; Brites, Ana; Gomes, Rita; Henriques, Patrícia; Gonçalves, Inês C.

23309 | Colonization and diversity of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* species complex (KpSC) in the healthy gut: The potential role of the food chain and lifestyle factors

Nova, Lúcia; Matos, Cátia; Gonzalez, Beatriz; Peixe, Luísa; Freitas, Ana R.; Novais, Carla; Antunes, Patrícia

Room A2 – Sport Sciences I

22781 | Is there any relationship between trunk incline and lower limbs' kinematics in non-expert swimmers during front crawl swimming?

Machado, Marta L.; Pserchia, Paul A.; Hamaoui, Alain; Vilas-Boas, João P.; Santos, Catarina C.; Costa, Mário J.

22923 | A Comparison of Internal and External Loads Between Training Drills and Official Games in Youth Basketball

Silva, Isadora; Gonçalves, Gonçalo; Neta, Paulo; Ribeiro, João; Guimarães, Eduardo

23434 | Lateral preference and proficiency in master swimmers

Felix, Mário; Correia, Sofia; Fernandes, Ricardo; Soares, Susana; Fernandes, Alexia; Pacheco, Matheus; Vasconcelos, Olga

23178 | How Students Perceive Teaching Processes: Insights from Teacher-Centered and Student-Centered Models

Vieira, Mariana; Mesquita, Isabel; Coutinho, Patrícia

Room A3 – Engineering I

22801 | Design and Optimization of CMOS Current-Mode Comparators: Analysis and Performance Trade-Offs

Monteiro, Gonçalo; Duarte, Cândido

23049 | Evaluating CMOS Digital-to-Analog Converter Architectures: A Comparative Study

Kulzer, Tomás G.; Cruz, Afonso; Duarte, Cândido

23399 | Optimized CMOS Design for Programmable Current Reference Circuits

Castro, Duarte; Monteiro, Gonçalo; Rainho, David; Khan, Hameed; Duarte, Cândido

23451 | Study of an Electronic Circuit Design of a Three/Two-Electrode Measuring Potentiostat System

Pino, Tiago M. V.; Khan, Hameed; Oliveira, Gabriel; Duarte, Cândido

23347 | Hybrid Calibration Mechanism for Duty-Cycle Correction

Reis, Matilde; Duarte, Cândido

Room A4 – Chemistry I

23011 | Nutritional Potential of *Tenebrio molitor* and *Zophobas morio* larvae: A Sustainable Alternative for Human Consumption

Machado, Susana; Lemos, Daniel; Costa, Anabela; Soares, Thiago F.; Oliveira, M. Beatriz P. P.; de Souza, Carolina Oliveira; Prieto, Miguel A.; Alves, Rita C.

22866 | Evaluation of ionic liquids as inhibitors of Cathepsin G activity: implications for chronic wounds management

Ribas, Inês R.; Mota, Fátima A. R.; Passos, Marieta L. C.; Santos, João L. M.; Saraiva, M. Lúcia M. F. S.

23255 | Electrochemical Preparation of Hydrogels for Sensing Applications

Oliveira, Eduardo; Mendes, João P.; Pereira, Carlos; Ribeiro, José

22785 | Design and synthesis of novel amino acid-derived gemini surfactants for RNA delivery

Cardoso, Pedro; do Vale, M. Luísa; Silva, Sandra G.

22683 | Green Aqueous Two-Phase Systems (ATPSs) based on choline salts and propan-1-ol: determination and modelling of phase equilibria

Sousa, Eduardo; Velho, Pedro; Moreira, Diogo; Coelho, José T.; Macedo, Eugénia A.

23404 | Improving honey authentication: Electrochemical genosensors for the detection of *Erica arborea* in commercial honey

Morais, Stephanie L.; Castanheira, Michelle S.; Santos, Marlene; Domingues, Valentina F.; Delerue-Matos, Cristina; Barroso, M. Fátima

Room A5 – Humanities and Social Sciences – Communication, Sociology and Geography

23258 | The Perceptions of LGBTQIAPN+ Consumers on Targeted Communication of Products and Services in the City of Porto.

Maciel, Plynio A.; Costa, Emília

23305 | Photo-documentary 'Futuro99': The Need of Narratives to Portray Utopias

Valencia, Sonia

23336 | The Pope's Kiss: John Paul II and the Expression of a Global Pontificate

Silva, João L.

22682 | Developing a temporal annotation scheme for clinical narratives in European Portuguese

Fernandes, Ana L.

22507 | Public Space and (De)Colonisation: A historical-ethnographic approach to Porto

Ribeiro, Carolina

22665 | The Cabinetmaker: between the craftsman and the operational worker

Ribeiro-Cruz, Catarina; Parente, Cristina

22846 | The influence of buildings on the urban microclimate: a case study from Espinho

Bird, Stephanie; Ramos, Inês; Ramalho, António; Silva, Raquel; Meira, Júlia

23338 | Resistance of Portuguese Urban Systems to Climate Change in Water Availability

Teixeira, Sara; Lima, Gabriela

10:30 - 11:30 **POSTER SESSION P1 – PISO 1**

Nº Chemistry

- 1 22708 | Innovation in Seafood Authentication: Combining Amino Acids and Artificial Intelligence**
Azeredo, Beatriz; Soares, Cristina; Paíga, Paula; Delerue-Matos, Cristina; Ramalhosa, Maria J.
- 3 22754 | Solid-phase peptide synthesis and structure elucidation of tetrapeptides**
Morais, André S.; Sousa, Emília; Fernandes, Carla
- 4 22784 | Synthesis and structure elucidation of a promising bioactive chitosan conjugate**
Morais, Ana B.; Lima, Rita; Tiritan, Maria E.; Pinto, Madalena; Fernandes, Carla
- 5 22814 | Design and synthesis of smart amino acid-derived gemini surfactants for Viral/infectious diseases**
Almeida, André; Silva, Sandra G.; Vale, M. Luísa

- 6 **22854 | Novel Biodegradable Depigmenting Agents: A Safe and Sustainable by Design Approach to the Environmental Concerns in Cosmetic Formulations**
Rodrigues, Abigail C.; Mota, Sandra F. S.; Cruz, Maria T.; Almeida, Isabel M.; Sousa, Maria E.
- 7 **22863 | Synthesis and structure elucidation of aminoalkoxy-substituted chalcones with potential biological activity**
Colli, Chiara; Assunção, Henrique C.; Pereira, Daniela; Cidade, Honorina
- 8 **22865 | Synthesis and structure elucidation of amino xanthenes**
Ghidoni, Francesca; Lima, Rita; Morais, Beatriz; Tiritan, Maria E.; Pinto, Madalena; Fernandes, Carla
- 9 **22873 | Initial Steps into the Synthesis of Siderophore-Antifungal Conjugates**
Rocha, Beatriz M.; Pinto, Eugénia; Sousa, Emília; Resende, Diana I.S.P.
- 10 **22914 | Exploring putative mechanism of action of mussel anti-settlement effect of antifouling agents: somatosensory transient receptor potential (TRP) ion channels**
Loureiro, Bruno S. M.; Gomes, Ana S.; Ruivo, Raquel; Silva, Marta C.
- 11 **22977 | AMPs in Action: Synthesis and in vitro Evaluation Against *Staphylococcus aureus***
Barroso, Cátia; Ferreira, Mariana; Gomes, Ana; Gameiro, Paula; Gomes, Paula
- 12 **23019 | Design of lipid-based nanoparticles for intranasal drug delivery to the central nervous system**
Borer, Ana; Granja, Andreia; Reis, Salette
- 13 **23044 | Development of Eco-friendly Nature-Based Antifouling Marine Coatings**
Costa, Catarina; Martins, Thaise; Sampaio, Ana R.; Correia-da-Silva, Marta
- 14 **23064 | Rational Design, Synthesis, and Biological Evaluation of Lithocholic Acid Conjugates for Application in Cancer Therapy**
Igreja-Cardoso, Maria B.; Rodríguez-Borges, José E.; Sampaio-Dias, Ivo E.; Vale, Nuno

№ Engineering

- 15 **22604 | An interactive tool for supporting university timetabling**
Tomás, Daniela S.; Pedroso, João P.
- 16 **22703 | Emotion Regulation in Children: Designing a Serious Game with a Co-Design Approach**
Carvalho, Bárbara; Silva, Eliana; Reis, Luís P.
- 17 **22709 | Sleep Microarchitecture Identification in the Shank3 KO Mouse Model of Autism Spectrum Disorder Through EGG-Guided Sleep Scoring**
Azevedo, Catarina P.; Falcão, Margarida; Monteiro, Patrícia; Jacinto, Luís
- 19 **22730 | Valorization of Textile Waste through Thermal Processes to Produce Adsorbents Materials**
Abreu, Leonardo T. S. F.; Pintor, Ariana; Soares, Olivia S.G.P.; Ferreira, Ricardo M.
- 20 **22735 | Co-Designing a Serious Game to promote emotional skills in adolescents in Residential Care**
Gomes, Pedro; Silva, Eliana; Reis, Luís P.; Sousa, Mariana
- 21 **22757 | Promoting Teacher Well-Being Through Gamification: A Co-Designed Emotion Regulation Tool**
Fang, David; Silva, Eliana; Reis, Luís P.
- 22 **22759 | Sustainable Utilization of Mine Waste: Enhancing Resource Recovery and Circular Economy**
Dias, Marcelo; Silva, Catarina; Silva, Pedro; Bento, Beatriz; Futuro, Aurora; Vila, Maria C.; Dinis, M. Lurdes
- 23 **22830 | Development of a nanof ormulation containing drugs with osseointegration and antimicrobial properties to improve the success of dental implantation**
Melo, Luísa; Pereira, Maria C.; Tavares, Maria P.; Loureiro, Joana
- 25 **22921 | Training Emotion Regulation Skills in Preschool Children: a Serious Game Approach**
Gonçalves, Catarina; Silva, Eliana; Reis, Luís P.
- 26 **22956 | Enhancing SIBs cell performance via cathode presodiation with sacrificial salts**
Saraiva, Carolina C. C. V.; Duarte, Miguel A.; Veloso, Rita C.
- 27 **22992 | Mineralurgical studies on Rare Earth Elements**
Magane, Anouk; Silva, A. Catarina; Vila, M. Cristina; Dinis, M. L.

- 29 **23025 | Identification and Quantification of Total Amino Acids in the Medicinal Plants *Passiflora incarnata* and *Valeriana officinalis***
Pereira, Liliana; Santos, Francisca; Nogueira, Maria Fernanda; Grosso, Clara; Soares, Cristina; Correia, Manuela; Amaral, Joana; Delarue-Matos, Cristina
- 30 **22953 | Optimization of an *in vitro* method for testing novel formulations for poultry meat sanitizing**
Sousa, Joana S.; Gomes, Inês B.; Simões, Manuel; Borges, Anabela

POSTER SESSION P1 – PISO 0

Nº Biological Sciences

- 41 **22678 | The endoplasmic reticulum enlarges in response to plasma membrane damage induced by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* infection and its pore-forming toxin, pneumolysin**
Beatriz Lopes; Joana Pereira; Sílvia Vale-Costa; Sandra Sousa
- 42 **22707 | Adaptations of *Aspergillus niger* to simulated Mars surface conditions**
Schiele, Alessa; Cortesão, Marta
- 43 **22786 | Genetic characterization of a Papillomavirus in the thornback skate (*Raja Clavata*)**
Fong, Denise C. S.
- 44 **22852 | Exploring deep-sea actinobacteria: unveiling biosurfactants for sustainable solutions**
Oliveira, Francisca; Carvalho, M. Fátima; Ribeiro, Inês
- 45 **22894 | Plastic Biodegradation by Microalgae: Molecular Prediction**
Lourenço, Diana; Pratas, Diogo; Sousa, Sérgio F.; Carneiro, João
- 46 **22896 | Microbiological Quality Evaluation of Untreated Drinking Water: Impact on Public Health**
Rodrigues, Inês; Godinho, Ofélia; Lage, Olga; Quinteira, Sandra
- 47 **22986 | Tracking Hepatitis E virus in Miranda donkeys: insights into viral presence and immunity**
Teixeira, Diogo; Pereira, Lorena; Abrantes, Joana; Lopes, Ana M.
- 48 **22993 | From soil to solution - a promising isolate with antimicrobial potential**
Ferrador, Liliane; Costa, Raquel; Gomes, Nelson G. M.; Grosso, Filipa; Peixe, Luísa
- 49 **22998 | Surveillance of zoonotic microsporidia in seafood and their implications for food safety and public health**
Afonso, Tatiana S.; Sousa, Carla D.; Valente, Luísa M.P.; Silva, Andreia F.; Gomes, Sónia
- 51 **23248 | Tracking *Escherichia coli* and the Spread of Resistance in Wastewater Treatment Plants**
Merêncio, Tiago; Godinho, Ofélia; Lage, Olga; Quinteira, Sandra

Nº Health Sciences

- 52 **22712 | *Staphylococcus* in the Oral Microbiome: Importance and Implications**
Fonseca, Maeva; Sampaio-Maia, Benedita
- 55 **22947 | Mycotoxins in Grains: A Hidden Threat to Health and Food Safety**
Gnatta, Gabriela; Yuaca, Anne; Gonzales, Beatriz; Kooistra, Clarice; Fernandes, Júlia; Fonseca, Marina; Antunes, Patrícia
- 56 **23020 | Meat Analogues, the new outbreak-free?**
Lopes, Diana; Mata, B.; Bastos, B.; Ferreira, C.; Silva, E.; Silva, J.; Antunes, Patrícia
- 57 **23249 | Development of an R Shiny Web-Based Application for Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance in Companion Animals**
Gonçalves, Marta; Vieira, Emanuel; Salgueiro, Sofia; Lopes-Jorge, J.M.; Niza Ribeiro, João; Pinello, Katia
- 58 **23389 | Poultry and Beyond: Progress and Challenges in Combating Antibiotic Resistance**
Castro, Ana C.; Monteiro, Ana M.; Ferreira, Beatriz; Neves, Guilherme; Oliveira, Mafalda; Antunes, Patrícia
- 59 **23447 | Biogeography of Oral Biofilm with NAM-FISH**
Rodrigues, Maria A.; Miranda, Sónia B.; Azevedo, Andreia S. M.; Gonçalves, Luzia C. M. M.

- 60 **22827 | Cutting-edge natural-based solutions to reduce *Campylobacter* contamination in poultry meat industry**
Tominac, Valentina; Gomes, B. Inês; Simões, Manuel; Borges, Anabela
- 61 **22650 | Mechanistic study on a novel nucleoside inhibitor of the coronavirus replication transcription complex**
Ramos, Bruno C.; Bakirtzoglou, Nikolai; Correia, Alexandra; Naesens, Lieve

Nº Sport Sciences

- 63 **22842 | Mental Training in Physical Education class: a study with secondary school students**
Pimentel, Raquel; Mesquita, Isabel; Mesquita-da-Silva, Sara; Bessa, Cristiana
- 64 **22855 | To Sample or to Specialise? Sport Participation Patterns of Youth Team Sport Male Players**
Sousa, Sérgio; Mesquita, Isabel; Coutinho, Patrícia
- 65 **22895 | Short vs long course swimming: analyzing the 1500 m performance differential in open water and pool specialists**
Pimentel, Marta; Fernandes, Ricardo J.; Carvalho, Diogo D.; Santos, Catarina C.; Costa, Mário J.
- 66 **22973 | Parental Influences on Fear of Failure in Youth Male Team Sports**
Barbosa, Nelson B.; Mesquita, Isabel M.; Fonseca, António F.; Coutinho, Patrícia C.
- 67 **23023 | From direct instruction to peer teaching: Developing physical literacy in swimming lessons in physical education**
Carvalho, Gabriel; Vieira, Daniel; Cardoso, Ana; Batista, Paula
- 68 **23199 | Video Feedback as an Innovative Pedagogical Tool for Teaching and Learning Gymnastics in School Contexts**
Silva, Carolina; Mesquita, Isabel; Bessa, Cristiana
- 69 **23329 | The Effect of Knowledge of Performance Feedback on Passing Performance in Young Football Players**
Rocha, Pedro; Oliveira, Ricardo; Cochofel, Nuno; Maneira, David; Vasconcelos, Olga; Pacheco, Matheus M.
- 70 **23343 | The use of Snus in football practice - what a player should know**
Soares, Francisco
- 71 **23406 | Correlation between adherence to screen time recommendations and BMI in 3- and 4-year-old children: A subsample of the SUNRISE project**
Silva, Wilka J.

Nº Economics and Management

- 72 **22674 | Effects of Leader Humour Styles on Psychological Safety, Employee Bootleg Innovation and Absorptive Capacity**
Vieira, Marta; Oliveira, Eduardo
- 73 **22758 | How Green is Porto's Business Landscape?**
Rodrigues, Beatriz; Paço, Cátia; Gomes, Mariana; Oliveira, Miguel

11:30 - 13:00 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS II**

Room A1 – Health Sciences II

- 22601 | Gentrification, physical environment and health: a combined analysis of the visual and textual materials of a Photovoice study conducted in Porto, Portugal**
Barateiro, Luísa; Silva, José P.; Ribeiro, Ana I.
- 22614 | Anthropometry, body composition, nutritional intake and eating behavior of transgender people**
Azevedo, Matheus; Poínhos, Rui; Pinhão, Sílvia; Almeida, Carla

22816 | Adverse Childhood Experiences and Pubertal Development in the Generation XXI cohort

Soares, Luna; Amorim, Mariana; Fraga, Sílvia

22913 | Addressing the missing link in obesity treatment: How chronotypes, eating speed and sleep quality shape body composition

Alexandre, Ana R.; Poínhos, Rui; Oliveira, Bruno; Correia, Flora

22945 | Risk of undernutrition assessed by the GNRI index and undernutrition identified by parameters suggestive of undernutrition

Matos, Catarina M.; Cascarejo, Sara; Melim, Diva; Oliveira, Bruno M.P.; Pinhão, Sílvia; Almeida, Jorge

22999 | Comparison of the MNA-FF tool and the GNRI and NRS-2002 indices for assessing nutritional status in patients admitted to an Internal Medicine Service

Cascarejo, Sara; Matos, Catarina M.; Melim, Diva; Oliveira, Bruno M.P.; Pinhão, Sílvia; Almeida, Jorge

23377 | Collaborative approach to HIV prevention: insights from a community-academia-healthcare partnership in Almada

Pereira, João L. L.; Vicente, Mariana; Rocha, Miguel; Gomes, Fátima; Pires, Cátia; Lages, Daniela; Gomes, André; Barros, Henrique; Meireles, Paula

Room A2 – Sport Sciences II

22746 | The influence of sports participation on health-related physical fitness changes in primary school children from the REACT study

Mota, Rui; Maia, José; Garganta, Rui; Farias, Cláudio; Tani, Go; Garbeloto, Fernando; Pereira, Sara

22937 | International Study of Physical Activity, Sedentary Behavior, and Sleep in Early Childhood (SUNRISE): a pilot study in Portugal

Amaral, Ricardo

23366 | Association of screen time with tangible and intangible parental screen-use behaviors in Portuguese preschoolers aged 3-4 years

Roxo, Lucas P.; Martins, Clarice

23437 | The Move Air Project

Sousa, Miguel; Rufo, João; Santos, Maria P.; Ribeiro, Ana I.; Martins, Clarice

Room A3 – Engineering II

23038 | Programmable Signal Generator based on a Gilbert-Cell Multiplier Circuit

Pinto, Guilherme; Duarte, Cândido

22606 | Automated Segmentation of Primary and Secondary Leaf Veins Using U-Net with ResNet-34 Encoder

Guedes, João M. C.; Gonçalves, Tiago F. S.

22802 | A Serious Game - Long Wall Exploitation

Reis, Vasco; Masyanganhe, Nancy; J. Santos Baptista; J. Duarte

23098 | A Serious Game for Enhancing Well-Being in Older Adults

Pinto, Marcos W. F.; Silva, Eliana; Reis, Luís Paulo; Silva, Vânia; Pedras, Susana

23005 | Deep Learning-Based Automatic Segmentation of Mandible in CT Imaging

Saraiva, Ana; Gouveia, Margarida; Lopes, Catarina; Pereira, Tania

23166 | Nodule-Centric CT-Based Deep Learning Models for Lung Cancer Survival Prediction

Amaro, Maria; Oliveira, Hélder P.; Pereira, Tania; Gouveia, Margarida

Room A4 – Chemistry II

22760 | Electrochemical Oxidation of Diclofenac: Two-Dimensional vs Three-Dimensional Degradation

Nogueira, Maria Fernanda; Caetano, Gabriela; Soares, Cristina; Correia, Manuela; Marrucho, Isabel; Delerue-Matos, Cristina

22950 | Repurposing plastic waste: terephthalate dihydrazide-based ligands with potential antibacterial properties

Moreira, Maria I. F.; Martins, Fábio; Ferreira, Mariana; Silva, Ana M. G.

22981 | Development of bis-rhodamine fluorescent sensors for metal ion detection: a sustainable approach using depolymerized plastic waste

Silva, João M. O.; Martins, Fábio; Gameiro, Paula; Silva, Ana M. G.

23245 | Bioaffinity of synthetic cannabinoids by high-performance affinity chromatography

Santos, Ana Rita M.G.; Cravo, Sara; Remião, Fernando; Fernandes, Carla

Room A5 – Humanities and Social Sciences – History

23327 | In the Sphere of the Jewish Colonization Project in Angola: Connections, Agents, and Vicissitudes (1912-14)

Silva, Miriam

23215 | The Great War on the socialist workers' press of Porto and Gaia (1914-1917)

Oliveira, Nuno

23279 | Women and the "New Man": The Female Presence in the Nationalist Discourse of MPLA (1956-1976)

Oliveira, Joana F.

22788 | "Abortion is not a Crime": from hypocrisy to the sacralization of the female body in Portugal (1976)

Abreu, B.

14:30 - 16:00 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS III**

Room A1 – Health Sciences III

22621 | Metabolic health before and after bariatric surgery: the impact of metabolic health definition

Plümacher, Anna; Dias, Cláudia C.; Peleteiro, Bárbara; Freitas, Paula; Fortuna, Inês; Lima, Eduardo; Martins, Elisabete; Martins, Maria J.

22667 | The Thermoneutrality Effect: A Comprehensive Study of its Influence on Mitochondrial Dysfunction in Alcohol-Associated Liver Disease

Pinheiro, Denise; Barrios, Monica; Martins, Maria J.; García-Ruiz, Carmen; Fernandez-Checa, José

22761 | Effect of Antidiabetic Drugs on Papillary Thyroid Carcinomas: An In Vitro Study

Gonçalves, Mariana B.; Castanho, Miguel S.; Jesus, Nuno; Soares, Paula; Máximo, Valdemar

22770 | Efficacy of Nutriscore and MST in identifying nutritional risk, using PG-SGA and GLIM criteria as the standard in outpatients with cancer

Ascensão, Maria I.; Oliveira, Bruno; Madureira, Elsa

22778 | The Effects of Anti-Diabetic Drugs on the Metabolism of Papillary Thyroid Cancer

Castanho, Miguel S.; Barreto Gonçalves, Mariana; Jesus, Nuno; Soares, Paula; Máximo, Valdemar

Room A2 – Sport Sciences III

23059 | Can a single session of motor imagery enhance performance in the execution of the transition phase of the muscle-up in intermediate calisthenics athletes?

Oliveira, Patrícia; Ramalho, João; Łozińska, Aleksandra; Cardoso, Francisca; Vasconcelos, Olga; Pacheco, Matheus

23099 | Comparison of kinematics and power to overcome drag between competitive triathletes and swimmers

Costa, Lawinya A.; Machado, Marta L.; Garrido, Nuno D.; Santos, Catarina C.; Costa, Mário J.

23453 | The Role of Autonomous Motivation in Planned Physical Activity and PA Craving: A Mediation and Moderation Analysis

Moreira, Maria M.; Ribeiro, Joana; Almeida, Maria João

23446 | Understanding front crawl efficiency: kinematic adaptations across swimming paces

Borda, Inês; Fernandes, Aléxia; Costa, Mário J.; Fernandes, Ricardo J.

Room A3 – Engineering III

23392 | Exploring biomaterials and new energy sources to develop self-powered electronic medical devices

Cardoso, Bernardo; Rocha, Sofia; Ventura, João O.; Pereira, A. M.; Gonçalves, Inês; Pereira, Andreia

23103 | Exploring polymers in triboelectric nanogenerators to advance bioelectronics

Teixeira, Carolina; Pereira, Andreia; Gonçalves, Inês; Mendes, Ana

22918 | Pyroelectric sensors based in polymeric nanocomposites for Smart Stents

Daniel, Ana; Machado, Inês; Pereira, André M.; Gonçalves, Inês; Pereira, Andreia; Rocha, Mariana

22917 | Inorganic-based pyroelectric sensors for stent restenosis continuous monitoring

Machado, Inês; Daniel, Ana; Gonçalves, Inês; Pereira, Andreia; Pereira, André; Rocha, Mariana

23226 | Disentanglement and Assessment of Shortcuts on Ophthalmological Retinal Imaging Exams

Fernandes, Leonor; Matos, João; Gonçalves, Tiago; Nakayama, Luis; Cardoso, Jaime S.

23337 | Enhanced Prediction of Aesthetic Outcomes in Breast Cancer Surgery Using Content-Based Image Retrieval and Collaborative Filtering

Ferreira, Pedro

23307 | Organic-inorganic hybrid materials as a tool towards alternative cancer treatments

Queiroz, Catarina P.; Ribeiro, Rui S.; Silva, Cláudia G.; Barros, Rita A. M.; Cristóvão, Raquel O.

Room A4 – Chemistry III

23200 | New hybrid carbon/bismuth oxide-based nanomaterials for smart energy harvesting and storage textile devices

Feiteira, Rúben; S. Teixeira, Joana; P. Queirós, Gabriela; M. Pereira, André; R. Pereira, Clara

23110 | Preparation and Catalytic Application of Bifunctional Porous Materials for CO₂ Valorization

Sampaio, César; Santos-Vieira, Isabel; Leo, Pedro; Pereira, Eulália; Balula, Salette S.

22725 | Eucalyptus Tree Bark-based carbons for application in sustainable batteries

Silva, Helena I. R.; Rodrigues, Ana R.; Costa, Renata; Brandão, Ana T.; Pereira, Carlos M.

22716 | Metal-Modified Biocarbon Composites from Peanut Shells for Energy Storage Applications

Rodrigues, Ana; Brandão, Ana T.S.C.; Pereira, Carlos; Costa, Renata

22807 | Application of miniaturised extraction techniques for the determination of VOCs in wood-based panels

Martins, Ana S.; Gonçalves, Fátima D.; Rodrigues, José A.; Ramos, Rui M.

22910 | Structural, Morphological, and Thermodynamic Studies of Thienoacenes for Electronic Applications

Silva, Soraia R. M. R.; Santos, Luís M. N. B. F.; Costa, José C. S.

Room A5 – Humanities and Social Sciences – Literature and Philosophy

22575 | Domingos Teixeira: the controversial portuguese historian

Correia, Mafalda

22862 | Voices of Transgression: Clytemnestra and Lady Macbeth

Custódio, Luísa R. F.

23319 | Ana Luísa Amaral: The Poetics of Memory

Schmidt, Rafaela A.

16:00 - 17:00 **POSTER SESSION P2 – PISO 1**

Nº Chemistry

1 23069 | Synthesis of 4'-methylchrysoeriol in order to obtain chiral flavone derivatives with promising antitumor activity

Zavatti, Camilla; Machado, João N.; Adriano, Gisela; Cravo, Sara; Pinto, Cláudia; Cidade, Honorina; Tiritan, Maria E.

- 2 **23073 | Lipid-based Nanoparticles for Oral Drug Administration: Stability in the Gastrointestinal Environment**
Santos, Beatriz; Granja, Andreia; Saraiva, Lucília; Reis, Salette
- 3 **23084 | Thermophysical properties of Iminodibenzyl and Iminostilbene**
Nogueira, Maria L.; Freitas, Vera L.S.; Ciccio, Andrea; Cipriotti, Stefano V.; Ribeiro-da-Silva, Maria
- 4 **23088 | Unraveling the Role of PAOPA γ -Lactam in the Allosteric Modulation of the D2 Receptors**
Gusmão-Dias, Tiago; Sampaio-Dias, Ivo E.; Rodríguez-Borges, José E.
- 5 **23096 | Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of α -Alkylated Proline Derivatives of Melanostatin Neuropeptide**
Moreira-Teixeira, Helena S.; Silva-Reis, Sara C.; Sampaio-Dias, Ivo E.
- 6 **23155 | Characterization of the kinetics and inhibition of thrombin by means of fluorometric analysis**
Kudryk, Catarina; Passos, Marieta L.C.; Mota, Fátima A.R.; Araújo, André R.T.S.; Saraiva, M. Lúcia
- 7 **23164 | Development of New Antibacterial Agents**
Rocha, Teresa; Nunes, Bárbara; Simões, Manuel; Borges, Fernanda; Cagide, Fernando
- 8 **23167 | Enantioseparation of Nadifloxacin and derivatives by an Amylose based Chiral stationary Phase**
Oliveira, Igor E.; Cravo, Sara; Ribeiro, Ana R. L.; Tiritan, Maria E.
- 9 **23193 | Comparative Analysis of Seaweed Extracts as Natural Antioxidants for Lipid Stability in Edible Oils**
Santos, Francisca; Soares, Cristina; Domingues, Valentina F.; Ramalhosa, Maria J.; Cação, Ana; Augusto, Helga; Delerue-Matos, Cristina
- 10 **23195 | Synthesis of chiral rhodamines derivatives for enantioselective fluorescent detection of amino acid in biological matrices**
Rodrigues, Maria J. S.; Tiritan, Maria E.; Silva, Eduarda M. P.
- 11 **23340 | Shrimp Shells Valorization: Chitin extraction using a mechanochemical methodology**
Pereira, Carolina P.; Ferreira, Juliana S.; Marques, Inês S.; Fernandes, Diana M.; Peixoto, Andreia
- 12 **23369 | Development of new biomass-based electrocatalysts for energy conversion reactions**
Alves, Daniela; Marques, Inês; Fernandes, Diana
- 13 **23370 | Photo-assisted production of ammonia using Fe₃O₄/g-C₃N₄ hybrid materials**
Monteiro, José M.; Lopes, Joana C.; Barros, Rita A.M.; Joy, Amala; Sampaio, Maria J.; Faria, Joaquim L.; Silva, Cláudia G.
- 14 **23402 | Detecting *Candida* spp. through an innovative genosensor**
Castanheira, Michelle; Morais, Stephanie; Lima, Luís; Santos, Marlene; Barroso, M. Fátima

Nº Humanities and Social Sciences

- 15 **22850 | The Sacralization of Thermal Waters in Gallaecia: The Case of the Nymphaeum of the Roman Baths of Chaves**
Miranda, Patrícia
- 17 **23228 | Indigenous ceramics from Castro de Guifões, Matosinhos: from unscheduled collections in the 1960s to contextualized exhumation, within the framework of the GUIFARQ Project. A Case Study**
Marques, Maria I.
- 18 **23274 | Therapeutic Waters in Gallaecia: Case study of Northern Portugal**
Madeira, Daniel
- 19 **22679 | Photography and Reconstruction of Architecture in Video Games**
Silva, Diogo
- 20 **22767 | The Epithets of Infanta D. Maria of Portugal (1521-1577)**
Gomes, Cristina
- 21 **23162 | Between Estates and Urban Agglomerates: Unveiling the Landscape of Alto Alentejo in Constant Construction**
Pinto, Magda A.
- 22 **22574 | Mental Health Literacy - Strengthening Competencies in Early Detection and Prevention**
Bola, J.
- 23 **22596 | A Narrative Approach to Populism**

Pereira, Francisco L.

- 24 **22955 | Professor and Physician Luís de Pina in the Foundation, Consolidation, and Leadership of Academic, Political-Administrative and Social Institutions**
Sousa-Teixeira, Susana; Andrade, José P.; Ricon-Ferraz, Amélia

POSTER SESSION P2 – PISO 0

Nº Health Sciences

- 41 **22576 | Knowledge, practices and attitudes of pregnant women during pregnancy: A Systematic Review**
Correia e Silva, Rita; Pereira, Maria L.; Frey-Furtado, Leonor
- 42 **22622 | Magnesium and metabolic health in individuals that underwent bariatric surgery**
Plümacher, Anna; Dias, Cláudia Camila; Peleteiro, Bárbara; Guelere, Bárbara; Freitas, Paula; Fortuna, Inês; Lima, Eduardo; Martins, Elisabete; Martins, Maria J.
- 43 **22670 | The influence of ankyloglossia on breastfeeding – a prevalence study**
Fernandes, Bárbara; Pérez, Amparo; Areias, Cristina
- 44 **22717 | Breastfeeding and bottle-feeding patterns and its influence on early childhood caries - a systematic review**
Pinto, Sara; Furtado, Leonor; Pereira, Maria de Lurdes
- 45 **22773 | Early-Life Exposure to Non-Nutritive Sweeteners: Impact on Adipose Tissue Morphology and Metabolic Function**
Oliveira-Barbosa, Margarida; Bracchi, Isabella; Keating, Elisa; Negrão, Rita
- 46 **22823 | Glutaminolysis as an Alternative Metabolic Pathway for Human Sperm Progressive Motility**
Gonçalves, Eva V.; Carrageta, David F.; Guerra-Carvalho, Bárbara; Cardoso-Moreira, Iara; Gonçalves, Ana; Barros, Alberto; Sousa, Mário; Bernardino, Raquel L.
- 47 **22870 | Adipose Tissue Bioenergetics Profile in Obesity-Related Dysglycemia**
Mendonça, Daniel A.; Bernardino, Raquel; Topete, Marcelo; Andrade, Sara; Pereira, Ana M.; Oliveira, Sofia B.; Costa, Madalena M.; Nora, Mário; Guimarães, Marta; Monteiro, Mariana P.; Pereira, Sofia S.
- 48 **22884 | Evaluation of the effects of Tocilizumab on Periodontitis and Peri-Implantitis: An *in vitro* Study**
Garcez, Isa M.; Martin, Victor; Gomes, Pedro G.
- 49 **22916 | Effects of TTR on cardiac angiogenesis – impact in Type 1 Diabetes (T1D)**
Barbosa, Joana; Gião, Tiago; Neves, João S.; Nogueira-Ferreira, Rita; Trindade, Fábio; Oliveira, Sandra M.; Luís, Carla; Soares, Raquel; Cardoso, Isabel; Almeida, Maria R.
- 50 **22922 | Association Between Maternal Cardiometabolic Risk Factors and Oral Health of Infants**
Pestana, Rebeca S.; Baptista, Manuel; Magalhães, Inês; Morais, Juliana; Ferreira, Ana Filipa; Marques, Sofia Cameron; Jerónimo, María Luís; Pinto, Carla; Sousa, Marta; Falcão-Pires, Inês; Duister, Denise; Zaura, Egija; Azevedo, Maria João; Sampaio Maia, Benedita
- 51 **22928 | Effectiveness of oral health educational programs in preventing dental caries in school-aged children - a Systematic Review**
Martins, Constança R. A. C.; Furtado, Leonor; Pereira, Maria de Lurdes
- 52 **22963 | Breastfeeding and Malocclusions: Characterization of a Pediatric Dentistry Population Enrolled in a Birth Cohort Study**
Marques, Sofia Cameron; Baptista, Manuel; Magalhães, Inês; Morais, Juliana; Ferreira, Ana F.; Pestana, Rebeca; Jerónimo, Maria L.; Pinto, Carla; Sousa, Marta; Falcão-Pires, Inês; Deuster, Denise; Zaura, Egija; Areias, Cristina; Sampaio Maia, Benedita
- 53 **22966 | Disarming Gingipains: A Novel Approach to Periodontal and Associated Systemic Diseases Management – A Systematic Review**
Pedrosa, Maria E.; Martin, Victor; Fernandes, Maria H.; Gomes, Pedro S.
- 54 **23012 | Computerized analysis of cardiocograms in cephalic vs breech presentation following the FIGO guidelines for fetal monitoring**
Teixeira, Ana; Gonçalves, Hernâni; Bernardes, João

- 55 **23055 | Structural Gastrointestinal Alterations in Diabetic Feline Patients: A Histopathological Approach**
Cardoso-Coutinho, Diogo; Esteves Monteiro, Marisa; Sofia Baptista, Cláudia; Landolt, Clara; Dias-Pereira, Patrícia; Duarte-Araújo. Margarida
- 56 **23057 | Potential influence of sex and age on serum annexin A1 levels in dogs: implications for inflammatory regulation**
Reis-Ferreira, Ana; Costa-Rodríguez, Noelia; Silva-Pereira, Carolina; Castanheira-Moreira, Joana; Vera-Rodríguez, Daniel; Brás-Silva, Carmen; Lobo, Luís; Sousa, Teresa; Montoya Alonso, José A.; Fontes-Sousa, Ana P.
- 57 **23075 | The metabolic impact of time-restricted eating and ketogenic diet: a systematic review of clinical trials**
Monteiro, Ana Margarida; Keating, Elisa
- 58 **23112 | Association between placental weight and birthweight, adjusted for parity, sex and PAPP-A levels: a retrospective cohort study**
Santos, Inês; Moreira, Rui; Gonçalves, Inês S.; Dias, Cláudia C.; Ramalho, Carla
- 59 **23157 | Metformin treatment decreases placenta fibrosis in a murine model of surgically-induced endometriosis**
Moreira, Anaisa; Rodrigues, A.R.; Gouveia, A.M.; Almeida, H.; Neto, A.C.; Neves, D.
- 60 **23172 | Hyperactivation of capacitating spermatozoa is suppressed by the follicular fluid of women with polycystic ovary syndrome**
Cardoso-Moreira, Iara; Gonçalves, Eva V.; Moreira, Mafalda V.; Guerra- Carvalho, Bárbara; Vale-Fernandes, Emídio; Sousa, Daniela; Brandão, Raquel; Leal, Carla; Damião, Isabel; Oliveira, Sara; Tavares, Inês; Monteiro, Mariana P.; Bernardino, Raquel L.; Carrageta, David F.
- 61 **23174 | Genetic insights into primary ovarian insufficiency: towards clinical utility**
Melo, Mariana; Sousa, Vanessa; Jorge, Paula; Alonso, Isabel
- 62 **23261 | Relationship between Mindful Eating and the Workplace Food Environment**
Taboada, Sónia; Poínhos, Rui; Torres, Sandra
- 63 **23263 | Achieving apical patency in non-surgical endodontic retreatment – an *ex-vivo* study**
Fernandes, Beatriz; Ferreira, Inês
- 64 **23348 | Relationship between the organic operation of SASUP canteens and the food supply of vending machines**
Ribeiro, Inês; Leite, Catarina; Direito, Madalena; Rocha, Ada; Oliveira, Bruno; Poínhos, Rui; Afonso, Cláudia
- 65 **23386 | Adherence to the Mediterranean diet among U.Porto students: study of associated sociodemographic and lifestyle characteristics**
Carvalho, M.; Dias, A.; Dias, V.
- 66 **23423 | Characterization of the food supply in vending machines at the University of Porto**
Santos, Carolina; Lousã, Mafalda; Silva, Beatriz; Pinto, Carolina; Poínhos, Rui; Oliveira, Bruno; Rocha, Ada; Afonso, Cláudia
- 67 **23428 | Multifunctional nanomedicines targeting the neonatal intestinal Fc receptor for enhancing the oral delivery of the antidiabetic peptide tirzepatide**
Almeida, João; Pinto, Soraia; Sarmiento, Bruno
- 68 **23432 | New Perspectives in Dental Caries Treatment: Integration of Minimally Invasive Approaches – A Systematic Review**
Meirinho, Mariana F.; Ferreira, João C.
- 69 **22806 | E Lactoferrin and Tetracyclines: A Dynamic Duo Against Oral Pathogens**
Abreu, Ana Raquel; Gomes, Pedro; Côrte-Real, Inês; Grenho, Liliana

17:00 - 18:30 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS IV**

Room A1 – Health Sciences IV

22694 | MiRNA downregulation dynamics during acquisition of enzalutamide resistance: Implications for early detection and RNA-based therapeutic approaches

Ferreira, Mariana; Morais, Mariana; Alves, Ângela; Tavares, Inês; Dias, Francisca; Bidarra, Sílvia; Medeiros, Rui; Teixeira, Ana L.

22702 | Hsa-miR-200c-3p, hsa-miR-25-3p and hsa-miR-301a-3p as potential biomarkers and therapeutic targets for restoration of PTEN expression in clear cell renal cell carcinoma
Alves, Ângela; Ferreira, Mariana; Eiras, Mariana; Lima, Luís; Medeiros, Rui; Teixeira, Ana L.; Dias, Francisca

22860 | Deciphering the Influence of CD276 glycodecode in Gastric Cancer Immunoregulation
Magalhães, Mariana; Gonçalves, Martina; Santos, Lúcio L.; Peixoto, Andreia; Ferreira, José A.

22864 | Deciphering AHR-melanoma code: From Sensing to Shaping the melanoma microenvironment

Santos, Cátia; Moreira, Beatriz; Berns, Matthew; Louphrasitthiphol, Pakavarin; Lian, Yilong; Goding, Colin; Moura-Alves, Pedro

22878 | Osteosarcoma-on-chip: A Gateway to Understanding Tumor Pathways and Metastatic Behaviour

Vieira, Carolina; Costa, Sofia; Sarmiento, Bruno; Pereira, Catarina L.

23016 | Establishment of a drug screening platform using patient-derived organoids from paediatric brain tumours

Esteves, Beatriz; Peixoto, Joana; Ferreira, Bárbara; Maia, André; Pombinho, António; Reis, Rita; Ferro, Anabela; Pinheiro, Jorge; Silva, Roberto; Pereira, Josué; Oliveira, Joana; Da-Cruz-Paula, Arnaud; Soares, Paula; Gil-da-Costa, Maria J.; Lima, Jorge

Room A3 – Engineering IV

23411 | Enhancing Liposomes Surface Modification for Efficient Blood-brain Barrier Penetration and Targeted Drug Delivery in Alzheimer's Treatment

Monteiro, Joana L.; Ramalho, Maria J.; Dabur, Meghna; Pereira, Maria C.; Loureiro, Joana A.

23266 | Nanostructured particles to target and treat Gram positive bacterial infections

Reis, Tiago; Andrade, Stéphanie; Pereira, Maria C.; Loureiro, Joana A.

22975 | Synergistic Approach to Wound Healing: Combining Natural Photosensitizers and Antiseptics

Silva, Catarina; Teixeira, Lília S.; Simões, Manuel; Borges, Anabela

23448 | Scaling up of a nanoformulation loaded with bioactive compounds for market implementation

Farinha, Rui P.; Nunes, Débora; Pinto, Leonor; Andrade, Stéphanie; Ramalho, Maria J.; Pereira, Maria C.; Loureiro, Joana A.

22652 | Aligning Education Systems' achievements with strategic goals for European Union countries

Osório, Fernando; Barbosa, Flávia; D' Inverno, Giovanna; Camanho, Ana S.

Quinta-feira, 8 de maio | Thursday, May 8th

08:00 - 18:00 Secretariado a todos os participantes/ *Secretariat for all participants*

09:00 - 10:30 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS V**

Room A1 – Health Sciences V

22874 | Long-term ketogenic diet aggravates behavior in aged male and female Wistar rats and impairs cognitive function in aged males

Gomes, Rita A.; Silva, Susana M.; Charrua, Ana

22936 | Transthyretin stabilization with Flufenamic acid: Novel approach to treat Alzheimer Disease

Machado, Beatriz; Gião, Tiago; Saavedra, Joana; Esposito, Cláudia; Arsequell, Gemma; Llop, Jordi; Cardoso, Isabel

22984 | Transthyretin (TTR) Activates Tissue-Specific Pathways in TTR Amyloidosis-Target Cells

Oliveira, João; Cardoso, Isabel; Almeida, M. Rosário

23077 | Exogenous administration of Delta-9-Tetrahydrocannabinol affects adult hippocampal neurotransmission in female Wistar rats

Neves, Ana M.; Leal, Sandra; Fonseca, Bruno M.; Sá, Susana I.

23092 | Impact of Oral Methylphenidate on Neuronal Outgrowth Markers in male and female juvenile Wistar Kyoto Rats

Soares-Couto, Patrícia; Costa, Vera M.; Dias-Carvalho, Ana; Sá, Susana I.; Ferreira, Mariana; Carvalho, Félix; Meisel, Andreas; Capela, João P.

23243 | Studying the amnesic effect of propofol/lidocaine in zebrafish

Velhinho, Fanny M. D.; Ferreira, Jorge; Olsson, Anna; Valentim, Ana M.

23417 | Early Diagnosis of Autism and its Implications for Child Neurodevelopment: A Systematic Review

Amadi, Michelle E.; Carvalho, Irene P.

Room A2 – Agrofood

23206 | Combined use of yeast exudates can prevent strawberry yield losses and improve resilience to fungal diseases

Lourenço, Pedro R.P.; Garrido, Andreia; Moura, Inês; Santos, Miguel; Fernandes, Tânia F.; Carvalho, Susana M.P.

23045 | Unveiling the Effects of Heat Stress on Plant Reproduction: Insights from *Arabidopsis* to Rice

Queirós, Ana R.; Higashiyama, Tetsuya; Coimbra, Sílvia; Pereira, Ana M.

22688 | Unlocking the proline puzzle: dynamics of its accumulation in *Solanum lycopersicum* L. under osmotic stress

Konrad, Clara; Martins, Maria; Nadais, Pedro; Spormann, Sofia; Soares, Cristiano; Fidalgo, Fernanda

22685 | Seed priming with melatonin of tomato plants co-exposed to glyphosate and Cu

Santos, Bruno; Martins, Maria; Fotopoulos, Vasileios; Fidalgo, Fernanda; Soares, Cristiano

22692 | Glyphosate-induced intergenerational effects on *Solanum lycopersicum* L. – insights into morphophysiological features and redox homeostasis

Cruz, Francisca M.; Sousa, Bruno; Fidalgo, Fernanda; Soares, Cristiano

22946 | Molecular detection of edible insects in foods: *Alphitobius diaperinus* larvae as a case

Santos, Filipa; Biltès, Rita; Teixeira, Carla S.S.; Villa, Caterina; Costa, Joana; Mafra, Isabel

23056 | Exploiting the effects of papain and microbial transglutaminase treatments on the potential allergenicity of *Tenebrio molitor*

Santos, Luís; Carriço-Sá, Bruno; Biltès, Rita; Dias, Catarina; Villa, Caterina; Teixeira, Carla; Mafra, Isabel; Costa, Joana

Room A3 – Engineering V

23359 | Purification of antileukemic biopharmaceuticals using carbon nanomaterials

Moreira, Francisco M.; Barros, Rita A.M.; Tavares, Ana P.M.; Ribeiro, Rui S.; Cristóvão, Raquel O.; Silva, Cláudia G.; Faria, Joaquim L.

23109 | Photocatalytic Ammonia Decomposition For Hydrogen Production Using Graphitic Carbon Nitride

Carneiro, Rafael C.; Lopes, Joana C.; Sampaio, Maria J.; Faria, Joaquim L.; Silva, Cláudia G.

22861 | Visible-light-driven selective production of p-anisaldehyde using GCN/Cs₃Bi₂Br₉

Ramos, Joana P.; Lopes, Joana C.; Sampaio, Maria J.; Faria, Joaquim L.; Silva, Cláudia G.

22857 | Electrochemical CO₂ Capture from Seawater: A Comprehensive Multiphysics Modeling and Simulation Study

Marramaque, Teresa P.; Afonso, Felipe; Mendes, Adélio; Azenha, Cátia; Pereira, Ana M. V. M.

22630 | Development of Co-Mo catalyst on CNT-HZSM-5 for the production of sustainable jet fuel

Magalhães, B.F.O.; Ferreira, K.K.; Ribeiro, L.S.; Pereira, M.F.R.

23163 | Optimizing Process Parameters for Manufacturing Porous Pure Iron Scaffolds Using Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF)

Lopes, Pedro; Silva, José; Alves, Jorge L.

Room A4 – Biological Sciences I

- 22690 | A novel approach to study the surface proteome of tripartite synapses
Ribeiro, Ricardo; Holt, Matthew; Pinto, Maria J.
- 22766 | Copine 1 counteracts pneumolysin-induced plasma membrane damage caused by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* infection
Monteiro, João; Lima, Ricardo; Vale-Costa, Sílvia; Sousa, Sandra
- 22951 | Structural and functional characterization of trimeric autotransporter adhesins from *Photobacterium damsela* subsp. *piscicida*
Viveiros, José; Lisboa, Johnny; Santos, Nuno M.S.; Vale, Ana
- 23182 | Aging profilin(g): links between the cytoskeleton and mitochondria-proteostasis
Correia, Miguel; Pinto, Inês Mendes; Zhou, Chuankai; Costa, Vítor
- 23211 | Lessons from Nature: Spiny Mouse (*Acomys*) Fibroblasts and Cardiac Regeneration
Cardona-Timoner, Maria; Silva, Elsa D.; Nascimento, Diana S.
- 23355 | Deciphering the Role of Cis-regulatory Elements in Glucose Homeostasis and T2D Development
Loureiro, Marco; Teixeira, Joana; Sousa, Diogo; Bao, Marta; Bessa, José
- 23364 | Unveiling MPS III through iPSCs: Paving the way for novel therapies
Gonçalves, Francisca; Almeida, Matilde; Gaspar, Paulo; Rocha, Hugo; Coutinho, Maria F.; Alves, Sandra

Room A5 – Humanities and Social Sciences – History and Archaeology

- 23219 | The «Cattle Prison» in the Castros Culture: Its archaeological context and integration into the Iron Age settlements of North-West Portugal
Duarte, Dinis B.
- 23292 | The erasure of imperial memory in the Roman Antiquity: *Damnatio Memoriae*
Nunes, Madalena M.
- 23168 | The defensive system of Santa Maria da Feira Castle: potential and limitations
Coimbra, Francisco M.P.
- 23076 | The *Negative Sanctio* in Medieval Documents up to 1200: The Spiritual Penalties in the «*Livro de Mumadona*» and the «*Liber Fidei Sanctae Bracarensis Ecclesiae*».
Veiga, Gabriela
- 23189 | The Perception of Sins Recognized by the Catholic Church through Portuguese Medieval Synods and Penances
Alves, Marta
- 22960 | From Moura to Lisbon: The Carmelite Order in the Medieval Portugal
Marques, António R.
- 23197 | The day-to-day life of the Portuguese North African Cities: A systematic survey of the military clashes between both worlds during the XV century
Costa, João M. B.
- 23303 | The Importance of Preserving Archaeological and Artistic Heritage: A Practical Approach at the Côa Museum
Neno, Juliana

10:30 - 11:30 **POSTER SESSION P3 – PISO 1**

Nº Agrofood

- 22689 | Investigating the role of Arabinogalactan Protein 3 (AGP3) during plant reproduction
Trancho, Júlia; Moreira, Diana; Ventura, Ana; Coimbra, Sílvia; Pereira, Ana M.
- 22691 | Multi-detection of veterinary medicines in animal feed for production
Lopes, Ana L.; Oliveira, Beatriz; Freitas, Andreia
- 22704 | Owner perspectives on the impact of diet on canine cardiac health

- Ferraz, Maria I.; Cabrita, Ana R. J.; Oliveira, Pedro; Pereira, Martim; Leal, Rodolfo O.; Rodrigues, Isilda; Fonseca, António J. M.; Duarte-Araújo, Margarida; Lobo, Luís; Fontes-Sousa, Ana P.
- 4 **22929 | Boosting wheat resilience to salt tolerance: the role of phytomicrobiome**
Ortolan, Natasha; Hilário, Sandra; Mariz-Ponte, Nuno; Bingobingo, Adriano; Fernandes, Tânia; Carvalho, Susana
 - 5 **23208 | Kiwi-Kiss: Paving the way for awakening sleeping beauty. Experimental approaches to find a proxy of the kiss of cold to break bud dormancy in kiwifruit**
Alcântara, Filipa; Sérvolo, Natália; Eiras, Clarisse; Campilho, Ana; Sottomayor; Mariana
 - 6 **23227 | Trophic interactions and predator diversity of *Phthorimaea absoluta*, a key pest of tomato.**
Silva, Ândria; Neto, Joana; Aguiar, Ana
 - 7 **23302 | Optimizing Polyphenols Extraction from Grape Stalks for Functional Food Applications**
Deweever, M.; Gonçalves M.; Soares C.; Moreira M.; Nouws H.
 - 8 **23390 | Low-trophic marine species, *Gammarus locusta* and *Hediste diversicolor*, as dietary supplements for gilthead seabream**
Monteiro, André; Canada, Paula; Moutinho, Sara; Calado, Ricardo; Valente, Luísa

Nº Engineering

- 9 **23047 | Seaweed Extracts as Natural Antioxidants to Reduce Lipid Oxidation in Edible Oils**
Rodrigues, Beatriz; Santos, Francisca; Soares, Cristina; Domingues, Valentina F.; Matos, Cristina D.
- 10 **23159 | Development of Competitive Serious Games as a Tool for Cognitive and Psychosocial Rehabilitation**
Pinto, Diogo C.; Pires, Rafael C.; Fernandes, Francisco R.; Neves, Diogo P.; Silva, Eliana M.; Reis, Luís P.
- 13 **23252 | Valorisation of Marble Sludge Waste in Construction: A Step Toward Circular Economy**
Monteiro, João; Vila, Maria C.; Dinis, M. Lurdes
- 14 **23253 | Key Strategies for Wastewater Treatment in Mineral Beneficiation of Rare Earth Ores**
Pinto, Fanézio; Vila, Maria C.; Dinis, M. Lurdes
- 16 **23354 | Contribution of design to the valorization of the waste of pine resin**
Afonso, Simão; Mendonça, Rui; Lima, Cláudia
- 17 **23358 | Exploring image segmentation techniques of unstained, brightfield kidney biopsy samples as a tool for assisting kidney disease diagnostics**
Carvalho, Mariana; Brandão, Isabel; Silva, Roberto; Lopes, Enzo; Zita, Yunnice; Oliveira, João P.; Alencastre, Inês S.; Cardoso, Jaime
- 19 **23391 | Neuronal Cell Membranes Protection by Caffeic Acid and Its Brain Delivery Enhancement Via Nanoencapsulation**
Barros, Sílvia; Loureiro, Joana A.; Ramalho, Maria João; Pereira, Maria C.; Andrade, Stéphanie
- 20 **23407 | Design and Implementation of a CMOS-RFIC Digital Doherty Transmitter**
Castro, Henrique
- 21 **23415 | Novel protein-based nanoparticles to transport drugs to the brain for the treatment of Alzheimer's Disease**
Rodrigues, Mariana; Carmo P, Maria; Silva, Ana Catarina; Loureiro, Joana A.
- 23 **23431 | Development of a water filter for the Aqua Leve jug.**
Lameira, Vasco; Mendonça, Rui; Lima, Claudia

Nº Geology

- 24 **22619 | New data on the middle Westphalian (Middle Pennsylvanian) macroflora from Alvarelhos, Trofa (NW Portugal)**
Ramos, Alexandre M.; Correia, Pedro; Pereira, Zélia
- 25 **23311 | The first occurrence of the rare drought-plant genus *Lesleya* (Spermatopsida) in the Buçaco Carboniferous Basin (Stephanian C, Western Iberia) and its paleoclimatic, paleoenvironmental and paleogeographic implications**
Börjesson, Lara; Pereira, Sofia; Correia, Pedro

Nº Health Sciences

- 41 **22605 | Parkinson and Neuroprotection: The Power of Ginkgo biloba**
Wang, Dália; Freitas, Isabella; Santos, Ema; Carvalho, Mariana
- 42 **22671 | Toward Electrophysiological Biomarkers for Adaptive Deep Brain Stimulation in Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder Patients**
Rodrigues, Larissa; Ferreira, Andreia; Pereira, Inês; Moreira, Ricardo; Jacinto, Luis
- 43 **22706 | Evaluating the Role of Neuron-Intrinsic Factors in the Regenerative Ability of the Spiny Mouse**
Gomes, Rafaela; Veríssimo, Eduardo; Silva, Tiago; Sousa, Monica
- 44 **22745 | Production of non-lamellar lyotropic liquid crystalline lipid nanoparticles for brain drug delivery**
Amorim, Ana; Granja, Andreia; Reis, Salette
- 45 **22771 | Mucoadhesive nanoparticles for brain delivery: repurposing drugs for glioblastoma therapy**
Rione, Carlota; Loureiro, Joana A.; Ramalho, Maria J.; Pereira, Maria Carmo
- 46 **22815 | Use of cannabidiol (CBD) for the treatment of anxiety**
Pinto, Sara; Oliveira, Beatriz; Fidalgo, Javier; Almeida, Hugo
- 47 **22858 | Invasive plant species and their neuroprotective potential**
Silva, Catarina; Alves, Tiago F.P.; Mateus, Nuno; Freitas, Vítor; Teixeira, Natércia
- 48 **22907 | Sumac, a forgotten spice with neuroprotection potential**
Couto, Ana R.; Alves, Tiago F.P.; Mateus, Nuno; Freitas, Victor; Natércia, Teixeira
- 49 **22971 | Invariant Natural Killer T (iNKT) cells characterization in Acid Sphingomyelinase Deficiency (ASMD) Patients under Enzyme Replacement Therapy (ERT)**
Andrade, João; Andrade, Catarina; Mondragão-Rodrigues, Inês; Cardoso, M. Teresa; Guimas, Arlindo; Chaves, Paulo; Aguiar, Patrício; Gomes, João; Maia, Tabita; Fonseca, Tiago; Macedo, M. Fátima
- 50 **23018 | Characterization of care related to Oral Health in individuals with Dementia: A cross-sectional study of informal caregiver's perspective**
Moura, Ana C.; Azevedo, Álvaro; Pereira, Maria L.
- 51 **23024 | Untangling sex differences in glia-to-neuron communication in chronic alcohol exposure**
Pacheco, Raquel; Canedo, Teresa; Rodrigues, Ana Margarida; Moreira, Joana; B. Relvas, João; Socodato, Renato; P. Vieira, Cristina; Summavielle, Teresa
- 52 **23091 | The role of digital technologies on intimate partner violence among young people: a study protocol**
Neto, Luísa; Moreira, Diana; Soares de Freitas, Cláudia; Pinto da Costa, Mariana
- 53 **23170 | Medical Imaging Metadata: Unlocking Their Potential for Clinical Research Evidence Generation**
Sebasteão, Susana L.; Pais, Mariana C.; Marques, Pedro V.
- 54 **23179 | Perfecting Peritoneal Dialysis: Designing a Cap for Catheter Disinfection**
Correia, Miguel; Monteiro, Catarina S.; Gonçalves, Inês C.; Henriques, Patrícia
- 55 **23180 | Inhibition of cholinergic neurotransmission by Cannabidiol (CBD) in the rat urinary bladder depends on the urothelium and involves TRPA1 channels activation**
Clemente, Daniela; Festa, Ana; Silva, Diogo; Correia-de-Sá, Paulo; Silva, Isabel
- 56 **23244 | Comparative analysis of different obturation techniques - *ex vivo* study**
Coutinho, Catarina; Ferreira, Inês
- 58 **23378 | Hypnosis in the treatment of Low Back Pain: Where are we? A Systematic Review**
Barbosa, Maria J.; Cardoso, Joana; Carvalho, Irene P.
- 59 **23262 | Processing and access to pathology archives: a metadata enrichment model**
Ramalho, A. Carolina
- 60 **23497 | Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors associated with the Mediterranean Dietary Pattern**
Peres, Maria J.; Gonçalves, Stefanie; Carvalho, Sofia; Trinca, Catarina; Santos, Natália

Room A1 – Health Sciences VI

22728 | Advancing preclinical research on Mycobacterium abscessus: Development of Biofilm and Animal models

Ribeiro, Mariana; Bento, Clara M.; Geerts, Lisa; de Vooght, Linda; Cos, Paul; Gomes, Maria Salomé; Silva, Tânia

22831 | Urocortin-2 as a novel biomarker of patient outcomes in HFpEF: A prospective cohort study

Vasconcelos, Inês; Adão, Rui; Vasques-Nóvoa, Francisco; Leite-Moreira, Adelino; Barros, António S.; Brás-Silva, Carmen

23232 | Pyroelectric Sensors for High-tech Cardiovascular Smart Stents

Marques, Inês; Pereira, André M.; Gonçalves, Inês; Pereira, Andreia; Rocha, Mariana

23281 | Decoding host-environment interactions in progressive pulmonary fibrosis: insights from hypersensitivity pneumonitis

Meneses, Alexandra; Cardoso, Catarina G.; Coelho, David B.; Melo, Natália; Mota, Patrícia C.; Guimarães, Susana; Moura, Conceição S.; Carvalho, André; Sokhatska, Oksana; Beltrão, Marília; Delgado, Luís; Morais, António; Saraiva, Margarida; Bastos, Hélder N.; Santos, Rita F.

23439 | How does an epithelial tissue prevent external forces from deforming it?

Novo, David; Osswald, Mariana; Morais de Sá, Eurico

Room A2 – Environment I

22775 | Characterization of dispersed organic matter from the Upper Triassic- Lower Jurassic of the Alcobaça area (Lusitanian Basin, Portugal): some paleoenvironmental considerations

Cunha, Jordany A.; Gonçalves, Paula A.; Flores, D.

22988 | Geochemical Exploration of aplite-pegmatitic veins in the North of Portugal: laboratory methods and GIS analysis

Varzim, Diogo; Sibó, Bárbara; Cardoso-Fernandes, Joana; Lima, Alexandre

23330 | Raw materials holistic recycling from Printed Circuit Boards

Soares, M. Vitória; Martelo, Liliana M.; Soares, Helena M. V. M.

23297 | Light-emitting diodes waste: potential of recovery all the raw materials

Brito, Filipa S.; Martelo, Liliana M.; Soares, Helena M. V. M.

22829 | Copper recovery from electronic waste through the organic solvent LIX 984N

Fernandes, Nelson; Cunha, Lídia; Futuro, Aurora; Soeiro, José; Sousa, Rui

22753 | Study of waste-based carbon dots for application in TiO₂-based photocatalytic nanocomposites

Silva, Diogo; Sendão, Ricardo; Pinto-Silva, Luís

Room A3 – Engineering VI

23420 | Optimizing Interfacial Stability in Sodium-Metal Batteries

Santos, Joana; Ferreira, João; Salgueiro, Tiago; Ventura, João; Duarte, Miguel; Oliveira, Joana

23158 | Eco-Friendly Hydrometallurgical Techniques for Gold Recovery: Alternatives to Cyanide Leaching

Pereira, João S.; Futuro, Aurora; Soeiro, José; Sousa, Rui; Azevedo, Andreia; Cunha, Lídia

22948 | Analysis of gold recovery with activated carbon

Silvestre, Erickson; Futuro, Aurora; Sousa, Rui; Carvalho, José; Cunha, Lídia; Azevedo, Andreia

22949 | Hydrometallurgical processes for the recovery and extraction of metals from ores

Paciente, Valente; Futuro, Aurora; Soeiro, José; Sousa, Rui; Azevedo, Andreia; Monteiro, Joana; Cunha, Lídia

23375 | Grape pomace as natural source for the electrocatalytic oxidation of pharmaceuticals

Costa, Amanda F.; Torres-Pinto, André; Silva, Adrián M.T.

23267 | Hardware Design for IMU Real-Time Data Processing

Muchanga, Angius; Duarte, Cândido

Room A4 – Biological Sciences II

22756 | Optimising microbial consortia for enhanced phytoremediation of cadmium and ketoprofen in estuarine sediments

Merchán, Julio; Perdigão, Rafaela; Fernandes, Joana P.; García, Loreto; Pereira, Margarida; Almeida, Marisa; Mucha, Ana P.

22840 | Do cetaceans have their mouthwatering? Gene erosion meets organ vestigiality

Artilheiro, Nádia; Valente, Raul; Ruivo, Raquel; Osório, Hugo; Castro, Filipe

22843 | A Novel Uncharacterized Mutation in Hawaiian Monk Seal PXR: A “Threat” or Adaptation?

Amorim, Inês; Oliveira, Diogo; Castro, Filipe; Ruivo, Raquel; Marques, Mónica

22880 | Engineering of Cyanobacterial Extracellular Vesicles for promoting Fish Health in Aquaculture

Teixeira, Beatriz; Matinha-Cardoso, Jorge; Oliveira, Paulo

23015 | Transcriptome analysis of a cyanobacterial strain and its new fatty acid incorporation pathway upon fatty acid supplementation

Sousa, Cristina; Kahn, Amaranta; Rego, Adriana; Leão, Pedro

23054 | Genetic Characterization of European Rabbit Subspecies in the Iberian Peninsula

Macieira, Carolina; Villafuerte, Rafael; Piorno, Vicente; Alves, Paulo Célio; Carneiro, Miguel; Queirós, João

23194 | Effects of temperature and salinity on asexual reproduction, strobilation and survival of *Catostylus tagi* polyps

Silva, Pedro F.; Lopes, João; Ferreira, Ana; Enes, Paula; Batista, Hugo

Room A5 – Criminology and Law I

22675 | Grandparentage investigation actions and the possible application of the limitation period in Article 1817 of the Portuguese Civil Code

Jucá, Marina C.B.L

22839 | Good Practices and Needs of Victims of Hate Crime and Violent Extremism: A Mixed-Methods Study

Costa, Inês; Sousa, Pedro; Moreira, Samuel; Santos, Margarida; Guedes, Inês

22700 | Data Protection and Cookies: The Planet49 Vs VZBV Case

Costa, Mafalda

22952 | How do individual and contextual factors explain online victimization of different types? A focus on protective behaviors.

Martins, Catarina; Guedes, Inês; Moreira, Samuel

23191 | After all, what does “consumer” really mean for the CJUE? – An appeal of a unitary concept of “consumer” in EU Law

Lee, Ka lao

14:30 - 16:00 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS VII**

Room A1 – Health Sciences VII

23006 | *In Vitro* Induction of Non-Enzymatic Post Translational Modifications in Serotransferrin

Amaral, Vera; Ramos, Eduardo; Silva, André

23052 | MicroRNA-Mediated Control of Mesenchymal Stem/Stromal Cell Senescence: A Comparative *in vitro* Study

Giestinhas, Andrea; Moura, Sara R.; Silva, Elsa; Nascimento, Diana; Almeida, Maria Inês

23251 | Advanced 3D Models for Breast Cancer: A New Frontier in Radiobiology Research

Nunes, B.; Canha-Borges, A.; Estevão, D.; Fernandes, R.; Paredes, J.; Deutsch, E.; Oliveira, M.J.; Castro, F.

23397 | Engineering a dual-reporter line to understand tissue tropism in *Leishmania infantum* infection

Faria, Carolina; Monteiro, Ricardo; Tavares, Joana

23412 | Combining Gastric Organoids and Stomach-on-a-Chip for Early Biomarker Discovery in Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer

Amaral, Beatriz F.

23421 | Complex *in vitro* model of the human lung barrier for applications in nanotoxicology

Fernandes, Ana B.; Remião, Fernando; Alfaro-Moreno, Ernesto; Vilas-Boas, Vânia

Room A2 – Environment II

22800 | Multi and Transgenerational Inheritance of Metformin: An Exploratory Study with the Amphipod *Gammarus locusta*

Neves, D.; Ribeiro, M.; Santos, M.; Barros, S.; Neuparth, T.

22810 | The Ecotoxicological Effects of Metformin on *Daphnia magna* and *Danio rerio* under global warming scenarios

Rojais, Marta; Rodrigues, Sara; Antunes, Sara C.

22819 | Assessment of stress-related biochemical parameters in *Arabidopsis thaliana* in response to silver

Soares, Leonel; Vasques, Gonçalo; Teixeira, Jorge

22693 | Lithium influence on phytochelatin synthase 1 and metallothioneins gene expression in *Arabidopsis thaliana*

Mota, Inês; Pereira, Cláudia; Teixeira, Jorge

22697 | *Arabidopsis thaliana*'s metallothioneins involvement in iron exposure and *in vivo* localization of AtMT2b in leaves of *Nicotiana tabacum*

Vasques, Gonçalo; Soares, Leonel; Mota, Inês; Pereira, Claudia; Teixeira, Jorge

Room A3 – Psychology and Education Sciences I

22698 | The Book Clubs as a space for Informal Adult education

Costa, Maria C.

23259 | Feasibility and acceptability of an online intervention with therapeutic assistance for parents of children with autism spectrum disorder in Chile: a case study

Chavarri, María; Cruz, Orlanda; Canário, Ana C.

23449 | Analyzing the European Union's environmental education policy cycle and its implications in the Portugal context through Critical Discourse Analysis

Santos, João F.; Silva, Sofia M.

Room A5 – Criminology and Law II

22599 | Exposure to community violence and juvenile delinquency: direct and indirect effects of guilt and shame

Teixeira, Beatriz; Santos, Margarida; Santos, Gilda

22872 | Individual Differences Among Hackers

Canudo, M.; Moreira, S.; Guedes, I.

22919 | Variations in police legitimacy perceptions across urban, semiurban and rural youth: results from a legal socialization study

Damas, Patrícia; Moreira, Samuel; Cardoso, Carla

23203 | Intimate partner violence as an opportunity for analysis: an overview of crime trends of the most prevalent crime in domestic violence

Tipakov, Miguel; Teixeira, Beatriz A.; Gomes, Hugo S.

23288 | Media use and children's and youth's externalizing and internalizing behaviors: the importance of parental monitoring

Couto, Gabriela; Cardoso, Carla; Santos, Gilda

16:00 - 17:00 **POSTER SESSION P4 – PISO 1**

Nº Environment

1 **22611 | Open field test in the evaluation of the behaviour of terrestrial isopods**

- Rabelo, Elyne; Teixeira, Cláudia; Alberto, Filipa; Abreu, Isabel O.; Bender, Isabelle; Guimarães, Ana T. B.; Ferreira, Nuno G. C.
- 2 **22653 | Zebrafish behavioural responses to simvastatin using colour preference tests**
Alberto, Filipa; Rabelo, Elyne; Teixeira, Cláudia; Abreu, Isabel O.; Guimarães, Ana T. B.; Carvalho, António P.; Ferreira, Nuno G.C.
 - 3 **22666 | From Agricultural Fields to Laboratory settings: assessing the impact of Altacor® insecticide to non-target aquatic organisms in a climate change scenario**
Marinho, Ana F.; Antunes, Sara C.; Rodrigues, Sara
 - 4 **22673 | Tannin-Based Coagulant Production: Green Alternative to Formaldehyde in the Mannich Reaction**
Moreira, Inês; Tomasi, Isabella; Boaventura, Rui A. R.; Botelho, Cidália
 - 5 **22696 | Biodiversity promotion measures for a renaturalization and preferential flooding zone – Corredor do Rio Leça**
Ferreira, Beatriz; Branco, Artur; Antunes, Sara C.
 - 6 **22727 | Aquatic invasive plants as natural filters of microplastics**
Ferrage, Letícia; Vieira, Luís R.; Iglesias, Isabel; Nogueira, Sandra; Kett, Gary F.; Antunes, Sara C.
 - 8 **22777 | The potential of algae extracts as dietary supplements: optimization and effects on *Daphnia magna* and *Daphnia longispina***
Pereira, Filipe; Antunes, Sara; Rodrigues, Sara
 - 9 **22825 | Monitoring metal and antibiotic resistance genes in estuarine environments**
Sionnet, Pierre; Fortunato, Gianuario; Pereira, Margarida; Perdigão, Rafaela; Almeida, Marisa; Mucha, Ana P.
 - 10 **22826 | Impact of human activities on the Leça river (Portugal): ecological status and macrolitter as an assessment tool**
Oliveira, Ana; Rodrigues, Sara; Nogueira, Sandra; Formigo, Nuno E.; Antunes, Sara C.
 - 11 **22989 | Effect of Forest Fires on Soil Bioremediation: Gondomar case study**
Pereira, Gonçalo; Vila, M. Cristina
 - 13 **23050 | Does Heat Stress Affect Hepatocyte Volume and Histology of Goldfish (*Carassius auratus*)?**
Moreira, Liliana A. O.; Rocha, Maria J.; Rocha, Eduardo
 - 15 **23113 | Assessment of Agri-Solar Roof Systems: Exploring Multifunctional Applications**
Costa, Isabella; Geraldés, Ana; Calheiros, Cristina
 - 16 **23291 | Development and Validation of an SPE-ESI-LC-MS method for portoamides quantification in seawater and the oyster (*Magallana gigas*) tissues.**
Évora, Luana; Oliveira, Isabel B.; Hinzmann, Mariana; Cunha, Isabel; Vasconcelos, Vitor; Almeida, Joana R.; Azevedo, Joana
 - 17 **23331 | Life cycle assessment of floating wetland islands for crop production**
Carrillo, Valentina; Pereira, Sofia; Afonso, Carlos A.; Calheiros, Cristina
 - 18 **23371 | Assessment of potential adverse effects of Carbon Blacks exposure in oligochaetes**
Costa, Verónica; Paiva, Cristiana; Machado, Diogo; Nogueira, Verónica; Pereira, Ruth; Cachada, Anabela

Nº Health Sciences

- 20 **22738 | Circulating miR-146a and Myxomatous Mitral Valve Disease in Dogs: Insights from a Comparison with NT-proBNP**
Reis-Ferreira, Ana; Santos-Gomes, Joana; Coelho-Pinho, Helena; Brás-Silva, Carmen; Lobo, Luís; Fontes-Sousa, Ana Patrícia
- 21 **22741 | Iron-doped calcium phosphate nanoparticles for enhanced bone regeneration**
García, Sofía; Grenho, Liliana; Fernandes, Maria H.; Santos, Catarina; Pérez-Amodio, Soledad
- 22 **22779 | Synthesis of chalcone derivatives with potential dual antimitotic and P-glycoprotein inhibitory effect**
Assunção, Henrique; Pereira, Daniela; Sousa, Maria; Hassan, Bousbaa; Cidade, Honorina
- 23 **22780 | Synthesis and characterization of kojic acid-chalcone hybrids as potential tyrosinase inhibitors for skin-lightening applications**
Gonçalves, Joana; Ferreira, Joana; Pereira, Daniela; Cravo, Sara; Quintas, Clara; Cidade, Honorina

- 24 **22821 | Universal adhesives – What is the most advantageous application in enamel and dentin? – Systematic Review**
Carreiro, Paula C.; Ferreira, João C.
- 25 **22905 | Apoptosis Levels in Cumulus Cells and Follicular Fluid: A Pilot Study**
Campos, Beatriz; Sousa, Vanessa; Oliveira, Cláudia; Neto, Nádia; Jorge, Paula
- 26 **22954 | NaDES Removal from Olive Pomace Extracts Using Solid-Phase Extraction**
Gong, An Q.; Soares, Thiago F.; Alves, Rita C.; Oliveira, M. Beatriz P. P.
- 27 **22982 | Is the inflammatory state the link between Cataracts and Age-related Macular Degeneration?**
Alves, Joana; Luís, Carla; Lima-Fontes, Mário
- 28 **23078 | A median artery piercing the median nerve in an adult human cadaver: an anatomical report**
Corrêa, Maria Eduarda; Madureira, Carolina M.; Rodrigues, António Pereira; Pinho, André Rodrigues; Madeira, M. Dulce; Pereira, Pedro A.
- 29 **23177 | Exploring Data Models: Use Of Real-World Data and OMOP Standards for the Development of a Wound Management Dashboard**
Palheira, Hélder A. S.; Canelas-Pais, Mariana; Taveira-Gomes, Tiago
- 30 **23230 | ViruScopeDB: a comprehensive multi-omics database for highly infectious viruses**
Lima, Ana; Carneiro, João; Sousa, Sérgio; Sá, Vítor; Pratas, Diogo
- 31 **23335 | Cellular models for the functional study of new variants in a Lysosomal Storage Disease.**
Monteiro, Beatriz; Monfregola, Jlenia; David, Hugo; Cardoso, Maria T.; Ballabio, Andrea; Alves, Sandra; Encarnação, Marisa
- 32 **23374 | Engineering a modified recombinant SPATR: implications in vaccines design for malaria**
Ramalho, Margarida; Neves, Filipa; Costa, David Mendes; Tavares, Joana
- 33 **23398 | Environmental Contaminant Exposures in Pets and their Owners: a comparative study**
Pinheiro, Ana Rita; Oliveira, Diana; Den Ouden, Fatima; Cleys, Paulien; Bosschaerts, Stijn; Pastorinho, M Ramiro; Niza-Ribeiro, João; Poma, Giulia; Covaci, Adrian; Sousa, Ana Catarina; Pinello, Katia
- 34 **23403 | Serious game in health education for radiodermatitis (RadGames)**
Matos, Marisa; Alves, Paulo; Vieira-Marques, Pedro

POSTER SESSION P4 – PISO 0

Nº Psychology and Education Sciences

- 41 **22763 | Perceptions Regarding Discrimination and the Rights of LGBTQIA+ People**
Algarinho, Beatriz; Pinto, Rafaela; Teixeira, Mandy
- 42 **22844 | Mathematical dialogue: The contribution of peer feedback to the development of mathematical strategies**
Ferreira, Ana M.; Lima, Louise
- 43 **22847 | Project-based work as an assessment tool: An experience with 11th grade students**
Cavadas, Bárbara; Ferreira, Rosa T.
- 44 **22882 | Students' engagement with a Gallery Walk: A study with 11th graders**
Sousa, Joana; Ferreira, Rosa T.
- 45 **22886 | Gallery 45²: representations in performing mathematical tasks**
Azevedo, Gustavo; Delgado, Fátima
- 46 **22897 | Feedback from GeoGebra for teachers and its influence on teaching practices**
Faria, Susana; Lima, Louise
- 47 **22898 | Students' difficulties in interpreting mathematical problem statements**
Simões, Tatiana; Ferreira, Rosa T.
- 48 **22901 | Students' use of self-assessment criteria to improve written mathematical communication in problem solving**
Mendes, Rita; Ferreira, Rosa T.
- 49 **22912 | Writing as a Tool for Promoting Mathematical Communication**
Pinho, Francisca; Delgado, Fátima

- 50 **23037 | The feminisation of higher education and the precariousness of technical-scientific professions**
Santos, Gabriela; Mazza, Mariana
- 51 **23040 | Technologies in Mathematics Education: Challenges and (Dis)advantages**
Oliveira, Diogo; Delgado, Fátima
- 52 **23239 | Feedback written in student productions: An experience through the Gallery Walk**
Sousa, Sofia C.; Lima, Louise
- 53 **23242 | Understanding geometric concepts: A teaching and learning experience using Geogebra**
Torres, Sónia; Lima, Louise
- 54 **23277 | The contribution of two-stage feedback in solving mathematical problems in mathematics A**
Sousa, Ana; Lima, Louise
- 55 **23285 | Peer Feedback and Collaborative Learning: Strategies to Improve Mathematical Communication**
Martins, João; Lima, Louise
- 56 **23405 | Project work in learning isometries**
Azevedo, André
- 58 **23027 | From paper to screens: Examining adolescents' writing motivation and performance in the digital age**
Silveira, Leonor; Alves, Rui; Chapouto, Diana; Vidal, Hugo; Oliveira, Isabela; Pinheiro, Micaela; Gomes, Raquel; Yamamoto, Luiza; Camacho, Ana
- 59 **23294 | Learning Words Through images: The Role of image dynamism, colorfulness, and Category**
Hassanpour, Fatemeh; Souza, Alessandra S.
- 60 **23333 | How do children understand intercultural situations? A qualitative study**
Tavares, Micaela; Guichard, Sofia; Cadima, Joana
- 61 **23413 | Adoption Communication Within Portuguese Adoptive Families: A Mixed Method Study**
Dias, Luiza; Soares, Joana; Barbosa-Ducharne, Maria
- 62 **23442 | Can personality traits predict substance use remission and relapse? A systematic review**
Ferreira, Daniela; Carvalho, Irene P.

Nº Criminology and Law

- 65 **22841 | Digital Risks and Adolescence: A Developmental Victimology Approach to Online Grooming**
Nápoles, Lara; Guedes, Inês S.; Santos, Margarida
- 66 **22867 | MAPSAFE: Mapping Perceptions of Safety and Fear Environments**
Afonso, Gabriel; Guedes, Inês
- 67 **22881 | Victim blaming: a study on public perceptions in cases of sexual assault**
Ferreira, B.; Guedes, I.
- 68 **23002 | Analysis of the macrostructural and gender-related determinants of violence indexes**
Araújo, Beatriz; Cardoso, Carla
- 69 **23357 | The Hidden Code: Unraveling Prison Misconduct**
Pereira, Tomás
- 70 **23363 | Fear of crime in rural environments**
Ferreira, Patrícia; Cardoso, Carla
- 71 **23376 | Knowledge is Power: Towards a Comprehensive Approach to Diminish Fake News Spread and Susceptibility**
Silva, B.; Cardoso, C.; Santos, G.; Castro, J.; Santos, M.; de Vilhena, M.; Moreira, S.; Guedes, I.

17:00 - 18:30 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS VIII**

Room A1 – Health Sciences VIII

23325 | Gene expression and proteomic analysis of the effect of chrysin and fructose on appetite and sweet taste preference of rats

Santos, Henrique M.; Martel, Fátima; Osório, Hugo; Andrade, Nelson

23346 | Uncovering the mechanisms of protection during *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection

Queirós, Sofia; Silva, Marta L.; Fernandes, Ana I.; Medina-Lopes, Monica; Saraiva, Margarida; Cardoso, Marcos

23367 | Modelling MPS III: Development of Cellular and Animal Models for Mucopolysaccharidosis Type III

Gonçalves, Francisca; Almeida, Matilde; Moreira, Luciana; Gaspar, Paulo; Rocha, Hugo; Martinez, Olga; Neuparth, Teresa; Soares, Joana; Ribeiro, Marta; Santos, Miguel; Pinho, Brígida R.; Oliveira, Nuno; Oliveira, Jorge M. A.; Coutinho, Maria F.; Alves, Sandra

23380 | Identification of Host Protective Mechanisms Induced by Interferon-Gamma in *Neospora caninum*-Infected Macrophages

Lima, Rui; Cardoso, Cláudia; Castro, Mariana; Miranda, Mariana; Almeida, Pedro; Pires, Luís; Vilanova, Manuel; Correia, Alexandra

23426 | Impact of Music Therapy on Family Caregivers in Pediatric Palliative Care: A Systematic Review

Delgado, Clara; Carvalho, Irene P.

23436 | Comparing Empathy Among Individuals with Borderline Personality Disorder and other Psychiatric Diagnoses: A Study in a Clinical Sample

Ferreira, Marta; Carvalho, Irene P.

22793 | Persistence of traumatic memories in early stage type 1 diabetic mice with Post-traumatic stress disorder

Cruz, Mariana F.; Munhoz, João; Fernandes, Helena; Correia-de-Sá, Paulo; Moreira-Rodrigues, Mónica

Room A2 – Environment III

22853 | Advanced Treatment in Constructed Wetlands: The Role of Photocatalytic Modules and Nanostructured Filters

Ojediran, Adetunji A.; Pereira, Sofia I.A.; Rosa-Santos, Paulo; Arenas, Francisco; Dolbeth, Marina; Ntougias, Spyros; Calheiros, Cristina S.C.

23250 | Monitoring Environmental Quality in Asprela Central Park: A Multi-Seasonal Study at different environmental compartments

Coelho, Tiago; Rodrigues, Sara; Nogueira, Sandra; Ribeiro, Helena

22724 | Ecological evaluation of the Douro Estuary: considering microplastics in ecological framework

Santos, Samuel; Vieira, Luis R.; Nogueira, Sandra; Iglesias, Isabel; Kett, Garry F.; Antunes, Sara C.

23299 | Uncovering the invisible: microplastics and their role in water quality in Portuguese reservoirs

Guimarães, Catarina; Pinto, Ivo; Antunes, Sara C.

23308 | Operational automatic detection, identification, and trajectory modelling of oil spills

Monteiro, Helena; Fernandes, Joana; Mota, Paul; Azevedo, Leonardo

Room A3 – Psychology and Education Sciences II

23017 | Academic Activism to Decolonize Higher Education in Portugal: an online analysis of student collectives' action

Perni, Alice; Menezes, Isabel; Coelho, Dalila P.

23070 | The silent struggles of figure skaters: A biopsychosocial perspective

Oliveira, Cristiana; Magalhães, Sofia; Limpo, Teresa; Leal, Teresa

23183 | Organizational Practices of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion for Neurodivergent Individuals: An Integrative Literature Review

Alves, Beatriz L.; Jordão, Filomena

Sexta-feira, 9 de maio | Friday, May 9th

08:00 - 18:00 Secretariado a todos os participantes/ *Secretariat for all participants*

09:00 - 10:30 PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS IX

Room A1 – Health Sciences IX

23287 | CRISPR\Cas9-mediated mutagenesis of enhancers to study the determinants of cis-regulation in endocrine pancreas

Nogueira, Tiago; Borges, Sofia; Nogueira, João; Ferreira, Fábio J.; Bessa, José

23312 | Predicting factors for no residual disease in breast cancer re-excision post breast conserving surgery: A ten-year cohort.

Borges, Leonor; Peleteiro, Bárbara; Mora, Henrique; Fougo, José L.

23313 | Spatial Mapping the Immune Landscape of Prostate Cancer Throughout Disease Progression

Costa, Mariana L.; Reis, Filipa D.; Cantante, Mariana; Henrique, Rui; Jerónimo, Carmen; Correia, Margareta P.

23318 | 4F-Bu3GalNAc as Novel Cancer Drug that inhibits the Biosynthesis of SLeX

Vale, Rosa; Costa, Ana F.; Vojtěch, Hamala; Reis, Celso A.; Jindřich, Karban; Gomes, Catarina

23324 | Dual-Particle Molecularly Imprinted Polymers for Fluorescent Detection of CA19-9: A Biomarker for Pancreatic Cancer

Rodrigues, E.; Piloto, A.M.L.

23388 | BBIT20 as a Novel Therapeutic Strategy for Prostate Cancer via Homologous Recombination Inhibition

Lima, Maria; Matos, Ana C.; Gonçalves, Vera; Ferreira, Maria J.; Jerónimo, Carmen; Saraiva, Lucília

Room A2 – Architecture I

22627 | Pulling Threads, Sewing Ideas. Textile as a Tool for Architectural Analysis, Thought and Representation

Perry, Sofia; Neiva, Ana

22612 | S. Torcato Sanctuary: 3D modelling of a 19th century design

Silva, Afonso; Varela, Pedro Azambuja; Marques, João L.

23051 | The role of travelling in architecture

Amaral, Salomé M.; Santos, André; Casanova, Maria J.

22659 | The relevance of practice in architecture learning: Design and Build as a comprehensive method

Ferreira, Marta; Rocha, Luciana; Rintala, Sami

Room A3 – Astronomy

22636 | Shedding light on the complexities of stellar rotation

Amaral, Juliana H.; Santos, Ângela R. G.; Cunha, Margarida M. S.; García, Rafael A.

22859 | Analysis of NIR activity indices for exoplanet detection and characterization

Monteiro, Telmo; Gomes da Silva, João; Delgado-Mena, Elisa; Santos, Nuno

23097 | Chromatic Doppler Tomography: A Novel Approach for Broadband Characterization of Exoplanet Atmospheres

A.F. de Melo e Sousa, M.; Cristo, E.; Santos, N.

22875 | Observational constraints on vector-like dark energy

Coelho, C. S. C. M.; Gschrey, A.-L. Y.; Martins, C. J. A. P.

22701 | Deviations from the von Laue Condition: Implications for the On-Shell Lagrangian of Particles and Fluids

Pinto, Samuel R.; Avelino, Pedro P.

22997 | Analytical Methods for Realistic Cosmic Strings and Superstrings

Barbosa, Pedro B.

Room A4 – Biological Sciences III

22871 | The unique morphology of seahorses and pipefishes: from genomes to phenotype

Garrido, Beatriz; Ruivo, Raquel; Monteiro, N.; Castro, L. Filipe C.

22964 | Kidney Agglomerulity in Toadfishes (Batrachoididae): recurrent gene loss and the origin of adaptation

Neto, Mariana; Oliveira, Diogo; Barros, David; Cordeiro, Miguel; Ruivo, Raquel; Castro, L. Filipe; Gomes-dos-Santos, André

23060 | The Anglerfish and the Kidney: the evolution of an Agglomerular kidney in Lophiiformes

Figueiredo, Filipa; Cordeiro, Miguel; Oliveira, Diogo; Castro, L. Filipe C.; Ruivo, Raquel

23169 | Colorful Evolution: Investigating the Evolutionary Foundations of Bird Ornamental Colors

Correia-da-Silva, Daniela; Ferreira, Pedro; Carneiro, Miguel; Pereira, Paulo

23241 | Morphological effects of marine bacteria in *Arabidopsis thaliana*

Silva, M. G.; Godinho, O.; Melo, P.; Lage, O.

23256 | From Ship to Shore: The Genetic Legacy of Invasive Rats in Atlantic Islands

Wielewski, Maryane; Gabriel, Sofia; Alves, Paulo C.; Vasconcelos, Raquel

23284 | From genomes to “heat”: the molecular origin of adaptation in desert mammals

Silva, André F.; Oliveira, Diogo; Machado, André M.; Ruivo, Raquel; Cordeiro, Miguel; Castro, L. Filipe C.

Room A5 – Arts I

22594 | Illustration as an Instrument for Education and Scientific Dissemination: Internship at the National Museum of Natural History and Science

Paixão, Francisca; Dolbeth, Júlio; Ferreira, Tânia

22684 | Sub-brand Design in the Cultural Context: Identity Design Project for the Education Service of the Soares dos Reis National Museum

Leite, Inês; Costa, Emília

22774 | Asprela Central Park: Articulation between Landscape Architecture and Editorial Design in the Representation of Narrative Flow

Reis, Maria; Costa, Emília

22732 | Pictograms as universal communication tools in drug administration: a graphic design project to improve health literacy

Brito, Sérgio; Costa, Emília

23063 | Integrating Plastic Film Recycling in Product Manufacturing: A Design Study on the Reuse of Low-Density Polyethylene

Moura, Teresa N.; Alves, Jorge L.

22731 | The multiple territories of illustration: Exploring its expansion into contemporary public art

Lemos, Margarida G.; Dolbeth, Júlio

10:30 - 11:30 **POSTER SESSION P5 – PISO 1**

Nº Biological Sciences

1 22660 | Wings of knowledge: Preserving the *Lepidoptera* collection at the Natural History and Science Museum of the University of Porto (MHNC-UP)

Marques, Cristiana; Grosso-Silva, José

2 22715 | A Green Sea Turtle’s Domain: Habitat Use and Preference in a Public Aquarium

Castelo, Maria; Ferreira, Ana; Magalhães, Ana

3 22776 | The demographic trajectory of the Iberian wolf using a population genomics approach

Nogueira, T.; Lobo, D.; Godinho, R.

4 22798 | Effects of methionine supplementation in the immune response of Atlantic Salmon (*Salmo salar*) against sea lice infection (*Lepeophtheirus salmonis*)

Pinto, Gonçalo P.; Machado, Marina M.; Vaz, Mariana V.; Nilsen, Frank N.

- 5 **22911 | Sustainable Space Habitats: Cyanobacterial Biomass as Feedstock for Fungal Biotechnology**
Sousa, Isabel S.; Verseux, Cyprien; Tamagnini, Paula; Magalhães, Catarina; Cortesão, Marta
- 6 **22920 | Engineering the Cyanobacterium *Synechocystis* for Biohydrogen Production**
Santos, Catarina; Pacheco, Catarina C; Tamagnini, Paula
- 7 **22958 | The evolution of the endemic pigeons of Macaronesia (*Columba* spp.)**
Sampaio, Gil; Gonçalves, David; Andrade, Pedro
- 8 **22996 | GC-MS Analysis of Water Contaminants in Algae Production – Insights from the INNOAQUA Project**
Magalhães, Pedro R.; Mendes, João P.; de Almeida, José M. M. M.; Coelho, Luís C. C.
- 9 **23010 | Saltmarsh plants revegetation potential to phytoremediate metal contamination in estuarine environments**
Souza, Ana; Garcia, Loreto; Cunha, Jacinto; Ramos, Sandra; Freitas, Vânia; Almeida, C. Marisa R.
- 10 **23021 | Functional Analysis of Plant Specific Inserts: Identification of Key Regions in Endomembrane Trafficking and Protein Interactions.**
Moura, Luana; Sampaio, Miguel; Neves, João; Pissara, José; Pereira, Cláudia
- 11 **23022 | Isolation and biochemical characterization of an environmental bacteria strain: Potential for caffeine degradation in coffee by-products**
Ferreira, Luana; Alves, Rita C.; Oliveira, M. Beatriz P. P.; Ferreira, Helena
- 12 **23034 | Biotechnological potential of cyanobacteria isolated from the Portuguese Coast**
Duarte, Aimone; de Rosa, Teresa; Oliveira, Flávio; Vasconcelos, Vitor; Lopes, Graciliana; Scotta Hentschke, Guilherme
- 13 **23053 | Development of a computational toolbox for data integration in environmental pathways analysis**
Simões, Diana; Machado, André; Lopes-Marques, Mónica; Carneiro, João; Neuparth, Teresa
- 14 **23071 | Identification of mako shark core areas at risk from fishing in the South Atlantic Ocean**
Santos, Inês; Vedor, Marisa; Queiroz, Nuno
- 15 **23100 | The Sampaio's Cabinet - Physical and Digital Curation of Specimens and Data for Biology, Botany, and Taxonomy Learning at the PO Herbarium (MHNC-UP)**
Vieira, Cristiana; Basílio, Pedro; Machado, Ana C; Fernandes, Íris; Pina, Madalena; Castro, Henrique
- 16 **23102 | Uncovering the trophic niche of the Little Bustard (*Tetrax tetrax*) in southern Iberia using a DNA metabarcoding approach to understand sex and seasonal differences**
Teixeira, Patrícia; Silva, João P.; Ferraz, Gonçalo; Pacheco, Carlos; Safara, Jorge; Venâncio, Luís; Alves, Paulo C.; Queirós, João
- 17 **23106 | Unravelling the impact of population reinforcements on the genetic variability of the Azorean Common Quail**
Almeida, Mariana; Andrade, Pedro; Rodrigues, Tiago; Leitão, Manuel; Gonçalves, David; Queirós, João
- 18 **23111 | Biogenic Hydrogels with Embedded Cyanobacteria for Marine Antifouling Applications**
Brante, Margarita; Gomes, Ana S.; Almeida, Joana R.
- 19 **23115 | Scytonemin-Producing Cyanobacteria from Morocco: Identification and Optimization of Growth Conditions**
Machado, Pedro M.; Castelo-Branco, Raquel; Gonçalves, Catarina; Urbatzka, Ralph; Vasconcelos, Vitor; Leão, Pedro N.
- 20 **23160 | Nutritional and Functional Value of the Macroalga *Ulva* sp. Cultivated in Aquaculture as an Ingredient for Food, Cosmetic, and Nutraceutical Products**
Novo, Matilde; Assunção, Joana; Aires, Duarte; Costa, Isabel
- 21 **23161 | Study of the Abundance and Sizes of species of limpet *Patella* in exposed and sheltered areas of Homem do Leme and Molhe beaches**
Ferreira, André F.
- 22 **23171 | A Non-invasive Approach to Hormone Analysis: Optimizing Blow Sampling in Cetaceans**
Lopes, Alice; Valente, Raul; Correia, Mafalda; Magalhães, Catarina; Costas, Benjamín; Ramos-Pinto, Lourenço
- 23 **23175 | Cyanobacterial Metabolites as Potential Antifouling Agents: Inhibitory Effects on Biofilm-Forming Marine Bacteria**

- Peeters, Hanne; Gonçalves, Catarina; Gomes, Ana S.; Almeida, Joana R.
- 24 **23176 | To adapt or not to adapt: the genetic underpinnings of adaptation of *Bombus terrestris* to distinct Portuguese biomes**
Nunes, Júlia; Pimenta, João; Melo-Ferreira, José; Pinto, Joana; Henriques, André; Paulo, Octávio; Boieiro, Mário; Ferreira, Sónia
- 25 **23185 | Taxonomic status of *Oecomys milleri*, a small rodent from the Brazilian Amazon**
Moutinho, Diogo A.; Rocha, R. G.
- 26 **23186 | Halopsychrophilic Cultures in Simulated Conditions of Icy Moons**
Santos, Catarina; Mota, Afonso; Santos, Nuno; Lage, Olga; Cortesão, Marta
- 27 **23188 | Production of Recombinant Ani s 1 Allergen for the Development of Immunodetection Methods for Fish Food Safety**
Martins, Ricardo N. M.
- 28 **23209 | A Computational Workflow for Exploring the Evolutionary Dynamics of Glutamine Homorepeats in Metazoa**
Correia, Rafael A.; Vieira, Jorge; Vieira, Cristina
- 29 **23210 | The SUMO E3 ligase SIZ1 at the core of plant development regulation**
Sorte, João; Lourenço, Tiago; Lisboa, Luísa; Freitas, Sara; Azevedo, Herlander; Castro, Pedro H.
- 30 **23216 | Population structure of the axillary seabream (*Pagellus acarne*) in Portugal mainland using otolith elemental signatures**
Kulzer, Rafael; Correia, Alberto T.; Schäfer, Christoph; Silva, Miguel
- 31 **23220 | Floating Islands as a Strategy for Promoting Biodiversity in Freshwater Ponds**
Graff, Lauren M.; Pereira, Sofia I.A.; Ilarri, Martina I.; Calheiros, Cristina S.C.
- 32 **23237 | Morphological and physiological characterization of two novel *Planctomycetota***
Castro, Catarina; Almeida, Eduarda; Godinho, Ofélia; Lage, Olga M.
- 33 **23247 | Stock discrimination of *Pagellus acarne* (Sparidae) in the Portuguese mainland waters using otolith microchemistry signatures**
Casaca, Ana; Kulzer, Rafael; Silva, Miguel; Mendes, Ana; Castro, Jorge P.; Schäfer, Christoph; Correia, Alberto T.
- 34 **23273 | Evaluating the Impact of Bacterial Extracts on Plant Growth**
Esteves, Daniel C.; Silva, Miguel; Godinho, Ofélia; Lage, Olga M.; Melo, Paula
- 35 **23283 | Optimizing Nutrition for Elasmobranchs A Study on Feeding Strategies to Improve Welfare in a Public Aquarium**
Rocha, Érica; Ferreira, Ana; Ozório, Rodrigo; Magalhães, Ana
- 36 **23289 | Development of an eDNA-qPCR assay for the detection and quantification of European-mink and American-mink in environmental samples**
Silva, Tatiana M.; Martins, Filipa M. S.; de Ayala, Ramón P.; Ruiz, Laura M.; Gómez, Asunción; Aranda, M. Carmen; Alves, Paulo C.; Queirós, João
- 37 **23300 | Extraction of astaxanthin from shrimp shells waste using bioderived deep eutectic solvents**
Sousa, Leonor; Favas, Rita; Marques, Inês S.; Sila, Ana C.; Peixoto, Andreia F.
- 38 **23304 | Conservation genetics of the European wildcat in the Iberian Peninsula: assessing genetic diversity and population structure to improve conservation strategies**
Correia, Diana; Alves, Paulo C.; Queirós, João
- 39 **23320 | Bacteria-plant interactions for bioremediation of estuarine sediments**
Nogueira, Tiago; Fernandes, Joana P.; Pereira, Margarida; Almeida, Marisa; Mucha, Ana P.
- 40 **23373 | Different Paths, Same Destination: Unveiling the Vacuolar Trafficking Mechanisms of Cardosins' Plant-Specific Inserts in *Arabidopsis thaliana***
Monteiro, João; Neves, João; Marcote, M. Jesús; Aniento, Fernando; Pissarra, José; Pereira, Cláudia

POSTER SESSION P5 – PISO 0

Nº Architecture

- 41 **22915 | The Movement in Architecture: Its Reflection and Influence on Social Condition**
Couto, Beatriz M. L.

- 43 **23265 | Experiences in the work of Távora and Siza - Part II**
Carneiro, Manuel J.; Furtado, Gonçalo
- 44 **22925 | FAUP in Viseu: Teaching & Anthropology of Space by Ricardo Pais**
Guedes, Maria J.; Furtado, Gonçalo M.
- 45 **23450 | Meeting between heritage and the project: Study of Vernacular elements and their integration into the present**
Pereira, Xavier S.L.G.

Nº Health Sciences

- 46 **22676 | Tumor organoid-based 3D models to uncover predictive biomarkers for breast cancer progression**
Ribeiro, Inês; Carvalho, Rita; Couto, Rita; Conde, Inês S.; Lapa, Alexandra; Duque, Carolina; Coimbra, Nuno; Paredes, Joana; Ribeiro, Ana S.
- 47 **22729 | Quercetin as a protective agent against silver nanoparticle-induced damage to human erythrocytes**
Santos, Inês; Sousa, Adelaide; Fernandes, Eduarda; Freitas, Marisa
- 48 **22739 | Impact of parabens on human leukocytes: assessment of cell viability and reactive species production**
Nicolau, Marta; Costa, Sofia; Ramalho, Ana; Fernandes, Eduarda; Freitas, Marisa
- 49 **22740 | Lemon verbena health products: Towards authenticity**
Aguar, Andreia; Veloso, Fernão; Martins, Raquel; Valentão, Patrícia
- 50 **22782 | In vitro 3D Cancer Spheroids: comparison of breast cancer cell lines from distinct molecular subtypes**
Maretti, Letícia; Castro, Maria Miguel; Esquivel, Catarina; Sousa, Barbara; Paredes, Joana
- 51 **22787 | Unveiling the Role of EVs-derived mir-15b-5p, -1293, -376a-3p in Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma Progression**
Dias, Vânia; Maurício, Joaquina; Morais, António; Medeiros, Rui; Teixeira, Ana Luísa; Dias, Francisca
- 52 **22817 | Computational Analysis of Unnarmicin Analogues**
Ribeiro, Matilde; Morais, André; Sousa, Emília; Fernandes, Carla
- 53 **22832 | Unravelling the interplay between colorectal cancer cell glycome and innate-like immune-cell response**
Carvalho, João; Pereira, João L.; Pinho, Salomé S.
- 54 **22938 | The role of IPO4 germline variants for breast/ovarian cancer predisposition in patients without mutations in known genes**
Ribeiro, Luís; Pinheiro, Manuela; Barbosa, Ana; Peixoto, Ana; Pinto, Carla; Santos, Catarina; Guerra, Joana; Teixeira, Manuel
- 55 **22967 | Development of an in vitro 3D Model of Osteosarcoma Based on Magnetic Cell Sheets and Tumor Spheroids**
Vendas, Sandro; Vinhas, Adriana; Gomes, Manuela E.
- 56 **22976 | Molecular Profiling of Prognostic Biomarkers in Melanoma**
Jesus, Marta; Costa, Catarina; João, Alexandre; Lopes, José Manuel; Barata, Catarina; Soares, Paula; Pópulo, Helena
- 57 **23001 | CtDNA sequencing as an alternative strategy to tumor tissue sequencing in metastatic prostate cancer patients in consideration for treatment with PARP inhibitors**
Costa, Anabela B.; Barbosa, Ana; Gonçalves, Cátia; Pinheiro, Manuela; Peixoto, Ana; Teixeira, Manuel
- 58 **23009 | The Impact of Hypoxia and Acidosis on Immune Checkpoint-related Proteins Expression in Melanoma Cell Lines**
Pereira, Matilde O.; Rodrigues, Catarina A.; Palmeira, Carlos; Santos, Lúcio L.; Vasconcelos, M. Helena
- 59 **23014 | Light Up Melanoma: design and optimization of curcumin nanoparticles for photodynamic therapy**
Tavares, Catarina; Reis, Salette; Nunes, Cláudia; Granja, Andreia; Marinho, Andreia
- 60 **23041 | Study of the relevance of antioxidant enzymes in thyroid cancer**

- Freitas, Sílvia; Peixoto, Joana; Máximo, Valdemar; Soares, Paula
- 61 **23042 | The cervical cancer screening programme in the North of Portugal: outcomes after nearly two decades of coexistence with the human papillomavirus vaccination**
Sá, Patrícia; Monteiro, Paula; Henrique, Rui; Lunet, Nuno
- 62 **23107 | Validation of genome-wide association studies (GWAS)-derived polymorphisms as susceptibility biomarkers for gastric cancer: a study design**
Mendes, Leonor; Lopes, Catarina; Dinis-Ribeiro, Mário; Pereira, Carina
- 63 **23184 | Exploring the antitumor activity of isoquinolinequinone N-oxides and of Selonsertib in pancreatic cancer cell lines**
Rodrigues, Rúben M. C.; Kruschel, Ryan D.; McCarthy, Florence O.; Vasconcelos, M. Helena; Xavier, Cristina P.R
- 64 **23382 | CDHR5 and UPB1 Promoter Methylation: Emerging Biomarkers for Sarcomatoid Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma**
Fernandes-Pontes, Fernanda; Constâncio, Vera; Lobo, João; Alzamora, Maria; Silva-Santos, Rui; Henrique, Rui; Miranda-Gonçalves, Vera; Jerónimo, Carmen
- 65 **23081 | Unraveling the Fungal Microbiome of kiwifruit affected by Esca in Portugal**
Silva, Guilherme; Gimranov, Emil; Santos, Conceição; Pereira-Dias, Leandro

Nº Arts

- 65 **22711 | The Fear that Transforms - Witches and their (Re)interpretations in Northern Portugal**
Duarte, Sara; Dolbeth, Júlio
- 67 **22736 | Design under market logic — A critical analysis of graphic design and its practice in an unequal society**
Carvalho, Cintia F. R.
- 68 **22813 | SANS SERIF: Visual Beginners Guide to Type Design**
Barros, Bruno; Amado, Pedro
- 69 **22961 | Filigree in the feminine: The Role of Women in Papermaking**
Antunes, Joana P.; Machado, Graciela; Dolbeth, Júlio
- 70 **22965 | Lá diz-se assim: Illustration of Porto's regional expressions**
Moreira, Andreia; Dolbeth, Júlio
- 72 **22994 | Brick chimneys in Greater Porto**
Soares, André; Ferreira, Cristina
- 73 **23039 | Considerations on Condensing Typefaces**
Sousa, Ribeiro
- 74 **23090 | Reading in color, feeling emotions – The psychology of color in Planeta Tangerina**
Silva, Sofia C.; Ferreira, Cristina F.
- 76 **23272 | The Evolution of Ukrainian Cyrillic: Historical Roots and Modern Digital Fonts**
Zavalniuk, Anastasiia; Amado, Pedro
- 77 **23295 | From Dust You Came and to a Dust Jacket You Shall Return: An Exploration of Books as a Method of Interment and Memorial**
Andres, Christine J.

11:30 - 13:00 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS X**

Room A1 – Humanities and Social Sciences - Political Sciences

- 22805 | The revolution will be digitalised: How echoes of Indigenous voices are restructuring digital diplomacy**
Pedrosa, Maria; Lima, Catarina
- 22812 | Memory Diplomacy or Diplomacy of Forgetting? The weight of history in Brazil, Colombia, and Mexico's foreign policy with the U.S.**
Albuquerque, Sara; Côrtes, Arthur; Gamba, Eduarda; Porto, Letícia
- 22856 | Where the Ocean Breathes: Strategic Diplomacy to Save Coral Reefs in Timor-Leste**

Freitas, Ana S.; Afonso, Ana S.; Gonçalves, Carolina M.; Costa, Maria I.

23218 | Rethinking the Tuvalu-Australia Falepili Union: Challenging Traditional Diplomacy in a Sinking World

Resende, Sofia; Neto, Beatriz; Oliveira, Jorge; Mourão, Andreia

Room A2 – Architecture II

22991 | The Vine, Wine, and Architecture in Bairrada's Cultural Affirmation

Cardoso, Marta; Lage, José A.

22959 | Gondomar's Washhouses: From Historical Recognition to a Strategy for Their Revaluation

Azevedo, Márcia

22968 | Bridging Rural Landscapes with Urban Growth: Regulating Land Use and Improving Infrastructure in Inguidé (Katembe, Mozambique)

Chicoco, Sámia K.

22851 | Unconventional Affordable Housing: Four experiences in Trieste

Lemos, Shanice

Room A3 – Astronomy, Mathematics and Physics

22987 | Galactic archaeology: Dissecting a Milky Way-like galaxy into its stellar populations

Vaca, Ricardo J.; Campante, Tiago L.; Neitzel, Andreas W.

23029 | Comparing Dark Energy Models in Extended Theories of Gravity

Monteiro, Paulo A. G.

23269 | Probing Unification Scenarios with Big Bang Nucleosynthesis

Dreyer, Iuna M.; Hilditch, David M.; Martins, Carlos J. A. P.

22762 | Fiber Optic System for Temperature and Relative Humidity Sensing in Concrete Structures

Faria, Rita; Silva, Pedro; Santos, André; Almeida, José; Coelho, Luís; Mendes, João

22608 | Semigroups Definable in O-Minimal Structures

Magalhães, Eduardo; Edmundo, Mário

23452 | Two Parameter Bound Differentiable Pruning – Introducing Trainable Hyperparameters in Neural Network Pruning

Pereira, Guilherme; Pedroso, João P.; Gouveia, Sónia

Room A4 – Biological Sciences IV

23165 | Exploring the main drivers of nest failure of steppe birds in Southern Iberian

Catarino, Francisco; Silva, João P.; Venâncio, Luis; Marques, Ana T.

23334 | Modeling variants of uncertain significance in *Caenorhabditis elegans* to reclassify pathogenicity in ciliopathies

Bakker, Jessie; Rocha, Sónia; Brouwer, Arjan P.M.; Dantas, Tiago J.; Abreu, Carla M. C.; Soares, Célia A.

23350 | Black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae oil as dietary lipid source for European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*): metabolic response to an acute stress challenge

Teixeira, Tito; Marques, Diana; Acebes, Daniel; Basto, Ana; Valente, Luísa M.P.

23360 | Dissecting the sensory defects of *bbs* mutants in *Caenorhabditis elegans*

Vitória, Filipa; Rocha, Sónia; Rocha, Helder; Abreu, Carla M. C.; Dantas, Tiago J.

23379 | Distribution and abundance patterns of amphibians in the Mindelo Ornithological Reserve, Portugal

Martins, Miguel; Naia, Marisa; Crottini, Angelica

23385 | Unraveling the association between SUMOylation and telomere functioning in plants

Lisboa, Luísa; Pires, Leandro; Lourenço, Tiago; Sorte, João; Freitas, Sara; Azevedo, Herlander; Castro, Pedro H.

Room A5 – Arts II

23231 | COLORS OF DISCOLORATION: A Reflection on the Visual and Affective Experience of Spaces in Decay

Cerqueira, Mariana M.

23207 | Women as the Personification of Evil: Witchcraft, Suffrage and Patriarchal Fear

Meira, Juliana

23095 | Memory and Understanding of the Self

Anjos, Verónica G.

22792 | Rehabilitation and Enhancement of the FBAUP Typography Workshop: Research, Inventory, and Promotion of Pedagogical Activities

Melo R.; Amado P.; Machado G.

22744 | The Colors of Alto Douro Vinhateiro: Documenting and Communicating Territorial Identity Through an Editorial Artifact

Ribeiro, Fátima; Costa, Emília

22609 | The continuous passage of time

Vázquez, Juncal A. C.

14:30 - 16:00 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS XI**

Room A1 – Humanities and Social Sciences – History of Art and Heritage Studies

23013 | «ELEGI LOCUM ISTUM MIHI IN DOMUM SACRIFICII»: The Church of Águas Santas and the transformations in a Romanesque building

Silva, Margarida

23061 | The Passion Triptych in the Chapter House of the Monastery of Santa Maria da Vitória

Madureira, Ana

23408 | The ‘Dance of Diplomacy’ in the 16th century: “Queen Elizabeth I Dancing with Robert Dudley”

Garcia, Luísa

23435 | The nineteenth century thuribles of the Porto Cathedral

Cardoso, Adriana

23425 | *Cosa Mentale*: The Conceptualization of Art and the Reconceptualization of Heritage

Guedes, Ana

23356 | Olga Roriz, Transformer of Images

Ferreira, Inês

22629 | Shaping Portuguese National Identity: Monuments and Memory in Porto (1800-1933)

Ramos, I.

Room A2 – Architecture III

22869 | Between Light and Shadow: A Phenomenological Exploration of Dwelling

Miranda, Sofia; Dias, José C.

22833 | The Metric as a project method

Oliveira, Sara C.

23264 | The Impact of a Centralized Living Room on the Organization of Domestic Space

Coelho, Ellis B. M.

23323 | Architecture of Change: The Potential of Wood for Flexible and Adaptable Projects

Hirade, M. Eduarda; Neves, António

Room A3 – Physics I

23441 | Innovating bioimaging through open-source microscopy: Hardware integration and software development of a Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscope

Seixas, Simão; Monteiro, Bruno; Azevedo, Maria Manuela; Sampaio, Paula

22726 | Fiber optic methane concentration measuring system based on a modified Wavelength Modulation Spectroscopy

Santini, Lorenzo; Coelho, Luís C.; Florida, Claudio

23086 | Unravelling Structural and Magnetic Phase Transitions in Gd₅(Si,Ge)₄: A Simultaneous Probing Approach

Andrade, Leonor; Soares, André M. R.; Araújo, João P. E.; Almeida, R.; Duarte, C.; Oliveira, G. N. P.; Belo, J. H.

22868 | Development of an Optical Sensing System for Monitoring Dissolved CO₂ in Aquaculture Environments

Lopes, Xavier; Coelho, Luis C. C.; Almeida, José M. M. M.; Mendes, João P.

22743 | The Influence of Incident Angle on SPR Response: An Optimization Approach

Rocha, Francisco; Mendes, João P.; Carvalho, João; Santos, André; Coelho, Luís C. C.; de Almeida, José M. M. M.

22695 | Hydrogen Optical Sensors for Leak Detection in Industrial Settings

Santos, André D.; Almeida, Miguel A. S.; Mendes, João P.; Almeida, José M. M. M. de; Coelho, Luís C.

Room A4 – Biological Sciences V

22848 | Development of engineered CRISPR knock-out organoid models to study gastric carcinogenesis

Moia, Eva; Santos-Ferreira, Liliana; Neto, João; Reis, Celso; Pinto, Filipe

23349 | Exploiting the bifunctional activity of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) to control the infection by *Ralstonia solanacearum* in tomato plants

Coelho, Hugo M. N.; Gimranov, Emil; Regalado, Laura; Pereira, Renato B.; Gomes, Paula; Santos, Conceição; Pereira-Dias, Leandro

23395 | Regulating Cardiac Regeneration Through Fibroblasts

Koolmees, Ilse; Gomes, Rita N.; Pinto-do-Ó, Perpetua; Nascimento, Diana S.

23396 | Thymic structure and cellular composition after T-cell lymphoma regression

Cunha, J.; Pacheco-Leyva, I.; Baessa, M.; Rodrigues-dos-Santos, N.

23352 | Using Deep Learning to Explain Cis-Regulatory Sequences

Magalhães, Francisco; Borges, Sofia; Nogueira, João M.; Ferreira, Fabio J.; Bessa, José

Room A5 – Arts III

23235 | I00k series: The Female Body as a Living Archive

Leça, Ana

23278 | Impregnations: artistic practice and multisensory perception upon the skin of the city

Mafra, Maíra

23306 | Peace, bread, and 50 years of (no) housing

Filho, J. A. T.

23387 | Cartographies of Absence: Body, Ruin, and Performativity in Contemporary Art

Rocha, Mariana M.

23416 | The Love for Things with Humour in Portugal

Antunes, Aldina

16:00 - 17:00 **POSTER SESSION P6 – PISO 1**

Nº Biological Sciences

- 22752 | Determining the impact of impaired acylation on the nervous tissue using novel mutant mice**
Torres, Guilherme; Alves, Nygell; Brites, Pedro
- 22755 | The power of the Portuguese Garden: Feijoa stems and leaves**
Boavista, Fabiana; Martins, Raquel; Valentão, Patrícia
- 22790 | Biological production of kiwiberry in Northern Portugal: Potential benefits against oxidative Stress**
Neves, Inês; Brito e Faro, Rosário; Martins, Raquel; Valentão, Patrícia
- 22791 | Physalis from the backyard: Unveiling its antidiabetic potential through bioactive compounds**

- Ferreira, Filipa; Martins, Raquel; Fernandes, Fátima; Valentão, Patrícia
- 5 **22892 | Functional analysis of knock-out mutants for aspartic proteinases A1, A2 and A3 from *Arabidopsis thaliana***
Silva, Pedro; Neves, João; Pissarra, José; Pereira, Ana M.; Pereira, Cláudia
 - 6 **23353 | Immunisation with a liposomal vaccine using *Neospora caninum* membrane proteins elicits a Th1/Th17-type specific response in cattle**
Castro, Mariana; Correia, Alexandra
 - 7 **22569 | Pyrolysis of Synthetic Cannabinoids: Identification of Combustion Byproducts Using GC-MS**
Pita, Filipa; Dinis-Oliveira, Ricardo; Guedes de Pinho, Paula; Carvalho, Félix
 - 8 **22662 | Using Single Molecule Tracking to understand how Ascl1-genome interactions are regulated by post-translational modifications**
Gaspar, Miguel O.; Almeida, Baltazar N.; Castro, Diogo S.
 - 9 **22664 | Uncovering the Skin-Boosting Power of *Actinidia arguta***
Brito e Faro, Rosário; Neves, Inês; Martins, Raquel; Valentão, Patrícia
 - 10 **22677 | The Unseen Side of Cannabis: A Dive into *Cannabis sativa* Root**
Araújo, José; Bernardo, João; Martins, Raquel; Paulo, Maria C.; Valentão, Patrícia
 - 11 **22749 | Translational potential of β 3gnt7 delivery to promote regeneration and functional recovery of the injured spinal cord**
Gonçalves, Laura; Braz, Sandra O.; Ferreira, Rafaela; Silva, Tiago; Cavadas, Bruno; Vieira, Cristina; Vieira, Jorge; Sousa, Mónica M.
 - 12 **22751 | Unravelling the pathology and disease mechanisms of the newly identified leukodystrophy caused by impaired choline transport**
Rocha, João; Silva, Tiago; Brites, Pedro
 - 13 **22811 | Approaching the activation of G-protein-coupled receptors in the study of Tenosynovial Giant Cell Tumor (TGCT) invasion**
Adão, Bárbara; Gonçalves, Ana I.; Gomes, Manuela E.
 - 14 **22887 | Development of Novel Pd-based Chemotherapeutic Strategies for Triple-negative Breast Cancer**
Silva, Daniela; Vojtek, Martin; Batista de Carvalho, Ana L.M.; Martins, Clara B.; Marques, M. Paula M.; Diniz, Carmen
 - 15 **22888 | Cannabigerol, a minor phytocannabinoid, impacts human endometrial stromal cell differentiation**
Sarmiento, Francisca; Alves, Patrícia; Sousa, Luísa G.; Fonseca, Bruno M.; Correia-da-Silva, Georgina
 - 16 **22899 | The impact of NGFR in bone pre-metastatic niche during Triple-negative breast cancer metastatic progression**
Couto, Rita; Conde, Inês; Ribeiro, Inês; Carvalho, Rita; Ribeiro, Ana; Paredes, Joana
 - 17 **22924 | Levodopa Reimagined - Molecular Innovations Against Ferroptosis-Induced Neurodegeneration**
Gonçalves, Tiago; Silva, Renata; Resende, Diana; Sousa, Maria E.
 - 18 **22926 | TissueExplorer - a user-friendly Bioinformatic Tool for Transcriptomic Data Analysis**
Rocha, Ana L.; Machado, André M.; Ruivo, Raquel; Marques, Mónica L.; Carneiro, João
 - 19 **22933 | Magnetic spheroids as 3D in vitro model for Chondrosarcoma**
Pereira, Erica; Vinhas, Adriana; Gomes, Manuela E.
 - 20 **22941 | The role of the hippocampus in coding time in associative memories**
Gonçalves, Clarisse; Fonseca, Rosalina
 - 21 **22974 | Neurotoxicity of new and old anticancer drugs on rat glioma C6 cell line *in vitro***
Alves, Tiago; Azevedo, Maria B.; Carvalho, Félix; Araújo, Margarida D.; Costa, Vera M.
 - 22 **23007 | Characterization of the machinery involved in protein import into peroxisomes**
Vilarinho, Beatriz G.; Francisco, Tânia; Pedrosa, Ana G.; Rodrigues, Tony A.; Azevedo, Jorge E.
 - 23 **23046 | Development and characterization of magnetic spheroids as advanced 3D tumor models**
Soares, Mariana; Gomes, Manuela; Zargarzadeh, Mehrzad; Oliveira, Vania C. C.
 - 24 **23066 | Preliminary Investigation of Chromosome Instability and DNA Repair in GATA2 deficiency**

- Fortes, Ailene; Oliveira, Cláudia; Neto, Nádia; Jorge, Paula
- 25 **23196 | Plasmonic nanolipogels for combined chemo/phototherapy of cancer**
Sá, Filipa C.; Granja, Andreia A.; Veloso, Sérgio R. S.; Coutinho, Elisabete M. S. C.
- 26 **23212 | Development of an *in vitro* skin cell model and comparison with *ex vivo* models: the case study of green cosmetic active ingredients**
Marques, Mariana; Teixeira, Filipa; Vieira, Mónica; Rodrigues, Francisca
- 27 **23217 | Evaluation of behavioral and neuroprotective effects of losartan in diabetic rats**
Silva, Joana; Teixeira, Fábio; Esteves-Monteiro, Marisa; Araújo, Margarida; Magalhães, Ana
- 28 **23326 | Characterization of mutations in the *RET* and *RAS* genes in Medullary Thyroid Carcinomas**
Almeida, Isabel M.; Martins, Rui S.; Soares, Paula; Vinagre, João
- 29 **23372 | Investigating the impact of protein O-GlcNAcylation on proteasomal degradation of Ascl1: role of the E3 ubiquitin ligase Huwe1**
Fernandes, B.; Azevedo, J.; Castro, Diogo S.
- 30 **23383 | Investigating formin's contribution to abscission**
Pereira, Catarina G.; Chan, Fung Y.; Carvalho, Ana X.
- 31 **23429 | Functional characterization of a novel PP1:SPINDLY holoenzyme**
Barbosa, J.; Gouveia, G.; Sunkel, C. E.; Bollen, M.; Conde, C.
- 32 **23004 | Integration of Multiple Data Sources on the Prediction of Harmful Algal Blooms Using Machine Learning**
Querido, Marco; Soares, Cristina

POSTER SESSION P6 – PISO 0

Nº Arts

- 42 **23328 | NOM[br]E. Historical development of the terminology used in the anatomy of the book Gaviria, Melissa**
- 43 **23332 | E-Waste in Product Design: from Obsolescence to the Creation of New Sustainable Products**
Portillo, G. J.; Mendonça, Rui; Lima, Cláudia
- 44 **23342 | Visual Identity in Music: Analysis of the graphic expression of José Afonso's discs from 1974 to 1985**
Aidos, Alexandra
- 45 **23351 | Transparencies: Design in the reuse of glass bottles**
Pinto, Catarina; Mendonça, Rui; Almeida, Teresa; Lima, Cláudia
- 46 **23368 | Isilda: Bridging Handwriting and Digital Typography**
Jardim, Laura
- 51 **23438 | Graphic Mapping of the Caminhos de Santiago: A Visual Journey through the Central and Coastal Routes**
Alves, Joana D.R.T.R.
- 52 **23440 | Peaceful Solitude - Illustrative Depictions of the Introverted Mind**
Ribeiro, Mafalda; Dolbeth, Julio
- 53 **23445 | The Influence of Moral Values on Artistic Expression: A Study on Institutional Constraints and Artist Autonomy**
Albergaria, Ana C.
- 54 **23454 | Bunker, the symbolic solution to being**
Amorim, Josefina

Nº Humanities and Social Sciences

- 55 **22617 | Impacts of the Urbanization Process in the city of Madrid: Climate Change Scenario**
Guedes, Sandra; Lousada, Luís; Monteiro, Vera; Oliveira Rocha, José; Rodrigues, Bruno;
Rodrigues, Joana

- 56 **23048 | Montalegre and Friday 13th: perceptions of tourists and residents**
Silva, Cristiana A. S.; Pereira, Pedro M. M.; Martins, Beatriz
- 57 **23257 | From Climate and City: Bioclimatic Comfort in Velásquez, Porto**
Bastos de Moura, Mafalda; Rodrigues Pinto, Daniel; Maia, Rafael; Pacheco, Maria; Valença, Maysa; Monteiro, Ana; Madureira, Helena
- 60 **22733 | The Dignity of Dialects: A Didactic Deconstruction of Northern Dialects**
Correia, Joana
- 61 **22985 | Loanword Adaptations and their Effects on the Syllable Structure of English Loanwords in Kusaal**
Gianfranchi, Guendalina
- 62 **23008 | The phonological adaptation of Tupi /i/ in Brazilian Portuguese: Patterns and influences**
Reis, Glória; Silva, Carlos
- 63 **23036 | Is Machine Translation of Clitic Pronouns from Spanish to European Portuguese Reliable?**
Almeida, Andreia
- 64 **23229 | Impoliteness and Forms of Address in Brazil's 2022 presidential debate**
Gonçalves, Ari; Ortiz, Cecília
- 65 **23293 | Recognition of Different Dialects of European Portuguese by PFL Students**
Fernandes, Lígia

Nº Astronomy, Mathematics and Physics

- 66 **23290 | Exoplanetary Interiors from Stellar Exteriors**
Kasperer, Hanna; Adibekyan, Vardan; Sousa, Sergio; Soares, Bárbara
- 67 **22876 | Development of optical sensors for monitoring concrete structures**
Monteiro, José L. C.; Da Silva, Pedro M.; Coelho, Luís C. C.; Mendes, João P.; De Almeida, José M. M.
- 68 **22906 | Study and development of a compact and standalone system to monitor water flow turbidity**
Reis, Alexandre M. L.; dos Santos, Paulo S. S.; Coelho, Luís C. C.; Mendes, João P.; De Almeida, José M. M.
- 70 **22962 | Study and Fabrication of Long Period Fiber Gratings for Sensing Applications**
Teixeira, Pilar G.; Mendes, João P.; Almeida, José M. M. M.; Coelho, Luís C. C.
- 71 **23030 | Magnetic and multifunctional nanostructures for theranostics applications**
Lopes, Ângela; Freitas, Sara; Belo, João; Silva, Ana; Crespo, Helder; Araújo, João; Sousa, Célia
- 72 **23031 | Study of Sodium Colour Centres in Diamond for Quantum Technologies Applications**
Santos, Guilherme J. C.; Araújo, João P.; Wahl, Ulrich; Correia, João G.; Pereira, Lino
- 73 **23414 | Laminated solid-state sodium-ion structural batteries with functionalised NaSICON electrolyte**
Almeida, António; Salgueiro, Tiago; Ventura, João; Camanho, Pedro; Oliveira, Joana
- 74 **23444 | Seawater Battery and Water Evaporation Power Integration for Enhanced Continuous Generation**
Spínola, Sara; Ferreira, João; Soares, Patrícia; Ventura, João; Espain de Oliveira, Joana
- 75 **23003 | Next-Generation Synthetic Face Data with Diffusion Models**
Salvador, Maria; Mamede, Rafael; Sequeira, Ana F.; Oliveira, Hélder
- 76 **23410 | Assessing the Goodness of Fit in Logistic Regression**
Branco, Ana I.; Gonçalves, Matilde; Gaio, Rita
- 77 **23443 | Reference Values for Vitamins Intake**
Saraiva, Beatriz; Pereira, Lara; Brito, Margarida; Gaio, Rita; Ribeiro, Ricardo

17:00 - 18:30 **PARALLEL ORAL SESSIONS XII**

Room A3 – Physics II

22893 | Metal salts doped polymer for soft artificial synapses

Ferreira, Pedro; Silva, Andreia V.; Ventura, João; Dias, Catarina

22680 | Beyond Crossbar Memristors: Nickel Nanowire Networks for Scalable Neuromorphic Computing

Lemos, Catarina; Ferreira, Pedro; Rocha, Mariana; Dias, Catarina; Ventura, João; Costa, Rui S.

23068 | Towards Hong-Ou-Mandel Microscopy for Birefringent Materials

Gonçalves, Carolina R.; Ferreira, Tiago D.; Silva, Nuno A.

23083 | Phase Transition Dynamics in NiMnIn: A Step Towards Efficient Magnetic Refrigeration

Soares, André M. R.; Andrade, Leonor; Araújo, João P. E.; Almeida, R; Duarte, C; Oliveira, G. N. P.; Belo, J.H.

23394 | The excitonic instability in 2D materials with nontrivial electronic topology

Miranda, Rui; Pereira, Vítor M.

23192 | Looking for Lambda

Gomes, José

Room A5 – Arts IV

23213 | Systems of Romance – Falling in Love with Virtual Characters

Pereira, João S.

23317 | Design and development of small sized pots for aromatic plants with sustainable concerns

Oliveira, Beatriz; Mendonça, Rui; Lima, Cláudia

23419 | Design contribution to the reuse of plastic collected from beaches: development of a sustainable lid for seafood trays

Proença, Tiago; Mendonça, Rui; Lima, Raquel

23455 | Between process and drawing: some considerations regarding the concept of reserve in drawing

Dias, Pedro

23282 | The psychoanalytic analysis of the creative impulse in figurative and abstract art

Saraiva, Diogo

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